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MASTER'S THESIS

**Analytical and experimental study of
chugging boiling instability: the CHUG
project**

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Abstract

One of the main aims of ESFR-SMART European project is the safety evaluation of a low-void Sodium Fast Reactor (SFR) core design, in particular the analysis of an unprotected loss of flow (ULOF) accident. Recent studies on the low-void SFR core show the occurrence of a stabilized chugging sodium boiling regime, that can be classified as a new safety measure acting as a level of defence preventing the severe accidents. In order to better understand and simulate the chugging boiling regime condition and to gather new experimental data, the ESFR-SMART project envisaged the construction of a new simple facility called CHUG to be planned and designed using water as sodium simulant.

The main purpose of this Master's Thesis has been the design and realisation of the experimental water rig facility "CHUG" for the study of the phenomenology of chugging boiling. This included also the conduction of the first tests and the comparison between the experimental data and the results from simulations performed with thermal-hydraulics code TRACE and PSI's in-house CFD code (PSI-BOIL). The test section consists of a vertical pipe of few-centimetre diameter filled with light water at ambient temperature and atmospheric pressure, where high-pressure steam is injected upwards from the lower part. Pressure at the bottom of the section and the axial stratification of the water temperature are tracked through the use of appropriate sensors. The interaction between the injected steam and cold water are analysed to study the conditions of the chugging boiling regime occurrence and condensation-induced pressure waves.

In parallel, analytical simulations of the experiment are conducted by the use of the thermal-hydraulics code TRACE to assess the validity of the code for the simulation of chugging boiling. Moreover, the behaviour of high-pressure steam bubbles in cold water will be investigated through the CFD code PSI-BOIL, highlighting the presence of inertia-driven bubble collapse and the partial suitability of water as sodium simulant.

The experimental results highlight that the chugging phenomenon is well reproduced by CHUG experimental facility. The variation of the level of injection allows the reproduction of several regimes of pressure oscillations, which are in accordance with previous studies on Direct Contact Condensation. The characteristic design of CHUG facility allows the reproduction of different oscillation patterns along the same test. In particular, the strongest pressure spikes (up to 5 bar) occur towards the end of each test, when the enhanced axial thermal stratification induces the formation of vapour slugs rising through the test section and collapsing in the upper low-temperature area. This may represent a way to mock up the oscillating behaviour of sodium boiling in low-void core concepts.

By comparing the experimental results with TRACE pre-calculations, it is proven that TRACE is able to reproduce the magnitude of the pressure peaks characteristic of chugging behaviour, but it is not capable of simulating the direct contact condensation phenomena occurring in the test section. In particular, TRACE predicts complete mixing of the water pool and no thermal stratification. This sets a difficult challenge for the simulation of thermally-stratified pools and the mock-up of real experimental conditions.

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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternate Current
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
ARDEC_o	ASTRID Research and Development European Collaboration
ASTRID	Advanced Sodium Technological Reactor for Industrial Demonstration
API	Application Programming Interface
BWR	Boiling Water Reactor
CEA	Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux énergies alternatives
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CFV	Cœur à Faible effet de réactivité en cas de Vidange du sodium
CHF	Critical Heat Flux
CIP-CSL2	Constrained Interpolated Profile method: Conservative Semi-Lagrangian 2 nd order
DAQ	Data Acquisition
DC	Direct Current
DMA	Direct Memory Access
DNS	Direct Numerical Simulation
ESFR-SMART .	European Sodium Fast Reactor Safety Measures Assessment and Research Tools
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FIFO	First-In First-Out
FV	Finite Volume
GIF	Generation IV International Forum
HTC	Heat Transfer Coefficient
IEPE	Integrated Electronic Piezoelectric Accelerometers
IHX	Intermediate Heat Exchanger
LOCA	Loss Of Coolant Accident
LWR	Light Water Reactor
MEB	Microbubble Emission Boiling
MOX	Mixed-Oxide fuel

MSMA	Multi-Scale Modelling Analysis
NI	National Instruments
PSI	Paul Scherrer Institut
RAM	Random Access Memory
RIA	Reactivity-Initiated Accident
SNAP	Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package
SFR	Sodium-cooled Fast Reactor
SVRE	Sodium Void Reactivity Effect
TC	Thermocouple
ULOF	Unprotected Loss Of Flow
VI	Virtual Instrument

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Chapter 1

Sodium-cooled Fast Reactors and safety aspects

1.1 IV Generation

As energy demand is continuously growing in the world, the energy industry is facing the challenge of providing an increasing amount of energy while at the same time having a minimum impact on carbon dioxide emissions. The R&D in the energy field, especially in the nuclear energy community, has been thus focused on new concepts for systems which have a strong economic and environmental sustainability. The Generation IV International Forum (GIF) is a co-operative international endeavour to develop the next generation of nuclear energy systems, which have to meet a set of defined requirements.

The main focus of fourth generation is the setup of a mix of different types of reactors providing enhanced safety and sustainability. A concept which was particularly developed in this framework is the design of fast reactors which are capable of converting a large majority of uranium-238 into plutonium-239 while producing electricity. A fast neutron spectrum shows indeed the special property of *breeding*, which consists of converting fertile isotopes (i.e. ^{232}Th or ^{238}U) into fissile isotopes (i.e. ^{233}U or ^{239}Pu) through neutron capture reactions so that the total inventory of fissile isotopes increases instead of decreasing during reactor operation. More precisely, the following nuclear reaction occurs:

The breeding property requires the neutron population both to sustain the nuclear reaction and to produce a sufficient quantity of fissile isotopes through capture reactions. This process is possible only at high energies, i.e. with a fast neutron spectrum, and would lead to the exploitation of more than 90% of natural uranium, rather than only 0.5 to 1% as in current light water reactors, multiplying the worldwide availability of primary fissile resources by more than 50 and increasing the sustainability of nuclear energy by taking advantage of the possible unlimited plutonium recycling [1].

A further challenge for Generation IV involves reducing the volume and the inherent long-term radioactivity of final waste. Fast reactors may indeed be capable of burning a significant part of the long-lived radioactive elements contained in radioactive waste, such as the minor actinides, which have a significant fission reaction cross section only at high energy.

The Generation IV International Forum (GIF) established the four main objectives that must characterize the future reactor systems as:

- **Sustainable:** using minimum natural resources and being environmentally friendly (limiting waste production in terms of radiotoxicity, mass, decay heat, etc.).
- **Cost-effective:** in terms of investment costs per installed kWe, the price of fuel, the cost of operating the facility, and consequently, the cost of electricity production which must be competitive in comparison with other energy sources.

- **Safe and reliable:** aiming for improvement compared with reactors currently in operation, while eliminating the need to evacuate the population from the site as much as possible, regardless of the cause and severity of the accident.
- **Proliferation resistant and protected against any external hazards.**

The Sodium-cooled Fast Reactor (SFR) concept is currently the only GEN IV reactor technology that is sufficiently mature and benefits from considerable feedback both in France, Russia, India, UK, Japan and overseas [2], associated with the potential to meet the GEN IV criteria. In particular, the ESFR-SMART project (European Sodium Fast Reactor Safety Measures Assessment and Research Tools) aims at further enhancing the safety of the commercial-size state-of-the-art design of SFR reactors [3], in strict cooperation with the ASTRID program conducted by CEA. Another main objective is the demonstration of advances on an industrial scale by qualifying innovative options, extrapolating the reactor characteristics to future industrial high-power SFRs, particularly in terms of safety and operability.

1.2 Introduction to neutronics

Before starting the description of the state-of-the-art SFR system, let's introduce briefly the basic principles of the energy production in a nuclear reactor, with particular attention to the quantities employed during safety analyses.

In a fission nuclear reactor, power production arises from the nuclear fission of fissile nuclei. A neutron-nucleus collision may result in a fission process involving the splitting of the heavy nucleus into several lighter nuclei along with the emission of prompt neutrons. As a consequence of this reaction, energy is produced both directly (i.e. kinetic energy of the resulting fission fragments and of the neutrons, prompt gamma radiation) and indirectly (i.e. radioactive decay of the fission products) amounting to approximately 200 MeV per fission. An example of nuclear reaction involving a neutron n and a ^{235}U nucleus is:

Thus, nuclear reactions involve the emission of several neutrons that allow the establishment of self-sustained chain reaction. The scope of a nuclear reactor is the control of the rate of the chain reaction in order to continuously produce energy.

A nuclear reactor core consists of the portion of a nuclear reactor containing the nuclear fuel components, rich of fissile nuclei and thus able to sustain a chain reaction. The fuel is typically made by low-enriched (up to 5% of ^{235}U) uranium oxide contained in fuel pins that constitute the fuel rods. In case of fast reactors such as SFRs, the fuel is made by a mixed oxide (MOX) of plutonium and uranium to enhance breeding properties. The fuel rods are grouped into assemblies, which play the role of keeping the distance between the rods in order to assure cooling and to provide structural support. The coolant flows through the core with the purpose of removing the heat produced by the nuclear reactions to convert the generated energy through a thermodynamic cycle.

The nuclear chain reaction is controlled by keeping the neutron population steady over time. The neutron population at any instant is a function of the neutron production (fission reactions) and the neutron losses, which are constituted by parasitic absorption in structural material, coolant or fuel itself, and leakage outside the core. When the neutron population remains steady from one generation to the next, the reactor core is said to be **critical**. The parameter which determines the criticality of a reactor is the **effective multiplication factor**, equal to the ratio of the neutron population at any generation with the one at the previous one. In other words:

$$k_{eff} = \frac{P}{A + L} \quad (1.3)$$

where P is the neutron production rate, A is the neutron absorption rate and L is the neutron leakage rate.

By its definition, it is easy to state that when k_{eff} is equal to 1 the reactor is said to be critical; on the other hand, if $k_{eff} < 1$ the reactor is *sub-critical* and characterized by a decreasing power level; finally, if $k_{eff} > 1$ the reactor is *super-critical* and characterized by an increasing power level.

During accidental sequences, the first concern is always to make sure that the chain reaction does not reach an uncontrolled state that would endanger the reactor structure provoking the release of radioactive material outside the containment. Thus, in reactor safety analyses it is often referred to another parameter which expresses the departure from criticality. This parameter is called **reactivity** and it is defined as:

$$\rho = \frac{k_{eff} - 1}{k_{eff}} \quad (1.4)$$

Again, when $\rho = 0$ the reactor is critical; when $\rho < 0$ it is sub-critical; when $\rho > 0$ it is super-critical. Reactivity is commonly expressed in *pcm* (per cent mille, equal to 10^{-5}) or in *dollars* (\$), namely in units of delayed neutron fraction β^1 .

In safety analyses, it is important to quantify the variation of reactivity in response to variation in core physical quantities, such as for example fuel temperature and coolant density. The change of characteristics may modify the critical equilibrium explained above and insert a positive or negative contribution to the reactivity of the core. According to the change in the reactivity, the variation of the considered physical quantity is said to have a positive feedback if the reactivity increases or a negative feedback if the reactivity decreases. The quantities that describe the reactivity response to the variation of core characteristics are the **reactivity feedback coefficients**. In general, the prevailing principle at the design step is to build the core in order to obtain stabilizing reactivity feedback coefficients with respect to the core critical conditions, in order to be able to control indirectly the chain reaction when an accidental situation occurs.

1.3 State-of-the-art in SFR Safety Analyses

1.3.1 SFR design

Regarding the design of Sodium-cooled Fast Reactors two main designs are currently taken into consideration: loop-type and pool-type.

The scheme of a loop-type SFR is shown in Figure 1.1. Loop-type design has the same principle of common nuclear reactor system. It includes three cooling circuits:

1. The primary circuit is the responsible for the cooling of the reactor active core. Cold sodium is injected at the bottom of the core where it flows upwards cooling down the fuel rods while at the same time being heated up. The resulting hot sodium is then sent to an external heat exchanger where it cools down by heating up the liquid sodium of the secondary loop. The primary sodium is then pumped back into the core and the loop continues.
2. The secondary circuit recirculates non-activated sodium and plays the role of providing the heat necessary for the steam generator to make the water in the tertiary circuit evaporate.
3. The tertiary circuit is the responsible for the generation of electricity, since it consists of the classic turbine-loop with steam generator, turbine and condenser.

It must be pointed out that the design of a secondary loop of sodium between the primary system and the turbine loop is envisaged for safety reasons. One of the main concerns related to SFR systems consists of the risk of water-sodium reaction: sodium is highly reactive with water and the potential contact between the two fluids may release a significant amount of energy and endanger the structural

¹The delayed neutron fraction β is the fraction of neutrons emitted by fission fragments long time after fission (typically after few seconds). They are distinguished from the prompt neutrons, whose emission occurs almost simultaneously with respect to the fission reaction. Although they account only for less than 1% of emitted neutrons, they are fundamental for the reactor control.

Figure 1.1: Scheme of a loop-type Sodium-cooled Fast Reactor (SFR).

integrity of the system. The water-sodium reaction risk is limited by special designs of the pipes and in general of all the components containing sodium. However, in the primary system, since sodium is in contact with the fissile fuel and faces directly the neutron flux, it may be activated. The design of a secondary sodium loop aims for the reduction of the potential radiological risk in case of contact between activated sodium and water inside the steam generator. The introduction of an intermediary loop, even if it decreases the efficiency of the cycle, is indeed safer since the water-sodium reaction risk involves non-activated sodium.

The scheme of a pool-type SFR system design is depicted in Figure 1.2. Pool-type reactor means that all the primary sodium coolant is contained inside the main vessel, where primary pumps and intermediate heat exchangers (IHX) are specially designed to be plunged through the reactor lid. The core contains the fissile fuel undergoing nuclear chain reaction and producing thermal energy. The energy produced by fission is deposited in the fuel in the form of heat and transported to the coolant (e.g. liquid sodium) that flows from the bottom to the top of the core, forced by internal pumps. The hot sodium then circulates through the intermediate heat exchanger where it transfers the energy to the secondary loop and gets cooled down. The cold sodium is then pumped again to the core and the cycle continues. A secondary loop runs secondary sodium from the IHX to steam generators, where it exchanges heat with a third circuit containing water, which plays the role of generating steam to be sent to the turbine for the conversion of thermal energy into electric energy.

The scheme of the pool-type primary sodium heat transport system is illustrated in Figure 1.3. The primary sodium system has three pumps and four intermediate heat exchangers (IHX). The fissile fuel is in form of fuel rods which are wrapped by an helicoidal wire inside sub-assemblies. Each sub-assembly constitutes a single closed channel: the cross-flow between the sub-assemblies within the core is not enabled. The sub-assemblies are fixed and supported by the diagrid, through which the primary sodium is pumped and forced into the core.

The primary vessel is physically divided in two parts: below, the cold pool collects the sodium from the IHX to be recirculated again through the core; above, the hot pool collects the sodium heat by the core to be sent to the IHX.

The ESRF-SMART project takes as benchmark reactor a 3600 MWth, sodium-cooled, mixed-oxide-fueled, pool-type fast commercial-size reactor prototype, with reference to previous design of ESRF

Figure 1.2: Scheme of a pool-type Sodium-cooled Fast Reactor (SFR).

reactor [4]. The primary and innovative objective of the state-of-the-art design is to obtain inherent safety with sufficiently large margins to sodium boiling and core melting during unprotected accidents, but also to be able to mitigate the consequences caused by severe accident scenarios.

1.3.2 Main safety issues for SFR

The aim of the SFR systems of IV generation is to reach a level of safety higher than in the past and at least equivalent to the nuclear reactors brought into operation during the same decade, i.e. 2020. The principal goal of nuclear safety is the protection of the population and its environment from potential radioactive material release, ensuring the containment of radioactive substances within the nuclear facility throughout its lifetime. Thus, SFR core design must be optimized with the scope of guaranteeing a natural behavior during transients aiming for the prevention and mitigation of severe accidents. The analysis on the natural behavior of the core during transients is focused on two main categories of accident scenarios: the accidents due to the insertion of reactivity, which envisage a loss of the control of the nuclear reaction and the accidents due to the loss of control of the core coolability.

The reactivity-initiated accidents (RIA) are characterized by the insertion of positive reactivity, leading to a sudden rise in the nuclear chain reaction rate and a subsequent jump in the core thermal power, which may endanger the integrity of the core. A typical RIA accident example is a control rod ejection, which is thoroughly analyzed i.e. in Light Water Reactors (LWR). In order to increase the stability of the core during this type of accidents, it is fundamental to achieve negative intrinsic reactivity feedback in operating conditions. Therefore, the characteristics of the core must be chosen so as the so-called Doppler feedback effect automatically limits any power excursion when the fuel temperature rises in the core.

However, in SFR systems an additional scenario may cause an insertion of reactivity: the sodium voiding inside the core. The most critical neutronic effect from the safety point of view is the so-called

Figure 1.3: Scheme of the primary system of a pool-type SFR.

”void-effect”.

The **sodium void reactivity effect (SVRE)** can be decomposed in the following components:

- **Spectrum hardening**, which has a positive reactivity effect. The decrease in moderation due to the decrease in sodium density leads the ratio between production and absorption reaction rates to be increased;
- **Decrease of absorption**, which has a positive reactivity effect since the neutrons previously absorbed by the coolant (i.e. sodium) become available to the fuel;
- **Enhancement of leakage**, which has a negative effect. The hardening of the spectrum leads the neutrons to increase their mean free path inside the core, enhancing the probability of exiting the system.

As regards the accidents scenarios due to failure of cooling of the core, they can be sorted according to their nature:

- Global, affecting the whole core, whose the main example is the Unprotected Loss Of Flow (ULOF), envisaging the unexpected sudden shutdown of the pumps (e.g. caused by a total station blackout) which may lead to the triggering of sodium boiling;
- Local, concerning one or several sub-assemblies and due to a localized failure of the pumping system.

It must be noticed that the ULOF transient is the most critical accident scenario threatening the core since it involves the safety issues of both reactivity induced and loss of cooling accidents. Thus, the analysis of the ULOF accident scenario requires the study of both neutronics and thermal hydraulics phenomena, which are strictly coupled.

Figure 1.4: Heterogeneous structure of the CFV core design [5].

1.3.3 Core designs to improve transient behaviour

The ESFR-SMART project focuses mainly on the development of a low void core concept which guarantees a promising safety improvement for the SFR design.

The development of a concept of an intrinsically safe core is based on the analysis and optimization of the reactivity feedback coefficients, that play a key role in the resistance of the core to degradation during the accident scenarios described above. The main purpose of R&D is thus the creation of a core concept with a weak sodium void effect, in order to minimize the consequences of a sodium voiding accident.

The main direction for the improvement of the sodium void effect is the maximization of neutron axial leakage and the minimization of the positive reactivity effects in case of sodium voiding. This is possible thanks to several expedients:

- The proportion between sodium and fuel inside the core can be decreased by reducing the diameter of the helicoidal wire assuring the spacing between the fuel rods. This leads to a decrease of neutron moderation during normal operation and causes the spectrum hardening and decrease of absorption positive reactivity effects to be lowered.
- The introduction of the so-called **sodium plenum**, namely a cavity filled with sodium during normal operation placed in each sub-assembly above the top of active fuel, promotes axial leakage in case of sodium voiding.
- A slab composed of neutron absorbers (B_4C) positioned above the sodium plenum results in additional absorption of neutrons leaking axially in case of voided sodium plenum configuration.
- The geometrical design of the so-called "**parfait**" core, where the core inner zone is axially subdivided in alternate layers of fissile and fertile materials, enhances the flux at the top of active fuel during normal operation. Based on the sodium temperature distribution, the most effective leakages will be at the top of the core, where the density of sodium is the lowest and the margin to boiling is minimum. In case of sodium boiling, the neutrons will tend to leak upwards. In order to maximize the leakage negative reactivity effect it is necessary to increase the flux at the upper boundary of the core: the use of the inner fertile blanket with adjusted thickness, position and radius allows a sufficient increase of the flux level at the upper surface.
- The disposition "**en creuset**", where the inner and outer fissile zones have different heights, allows increasing the neutron flux at the upper boundary of the inner core and consequently the axial leakage negative effect in case of sodium voiding.

All these design concepts are applied for example to the CFV (*Cœur à faible effet de réactivité en cas de vidange du sodium*) core design of ASTRID (Figure 1.4). By all these measures the void reactivity

feedback coefficient can be globally turned into negative.

The ESFR-SMART core contains all the design features to improve safety listed above, with the exception of the disposition "en creuset". These measure have appreciably lowered the total sodium void effect bringing it close to zero for a core with fresh fuel while not influencing substantially other core physics parameters [6].

1.3.4 Unprotected Loss Of Flow transient: CFV core design case

As already stated in Section 1.3.2, the Unprotected Loss Of Flow (ULOF) transient is a global accident scenario due to failure of cooling of the core.

In brief, the ULOF accident scenario is assumed to progress in the following way:

- Up to the moment of the triggering of the transient, the core produces the nominal thermal power at the end of fuel cycle, meaning that all control rods are withdrawn;
- The transient is triggered by the complete failure of the electricity along with the failure of all safety systems for reactivity control: the control and safety rods are not inserted into the core;
- The pump coast-down is modeled by the following formula:

$$H = H(t_0) \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{t}{\tau}} \right)^2 \quad (1.5)$$

where H is the pump head depending on time t , t_0 represents the instant of the ULOF initiation and τ is the mass flow halving time, which is assumed as equal to 10 seconds [7].

The main feature of the ULOF transient occurring in a low-void-effect SFR core is the strict and mutual relationship between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics. A multi-physics simulation is thus necessary for an accurate representation of the ULOF transient. For the simulation of this accident scenario, a simple Point Kinetics approach reveals to be incomplete. A Point Kinetics with fixed reactivity feedback coefficients model does not account for the local changes of neutronic parameters, such as the magnitude of the void feedback coefficient, caused by the boiling phenomenon affecting selectively the sub-assemblies. The sodium density feedback loses indeed its linearity as a function of sodium density in case of boiling.

In frame of CEA-PSI ASTRID R&D European Cooperation (ARDECo), an Unprotected Loss Of Flow accident (ULOF) transient occurring in a CFV core primary system at the End-of-Cycle was simulated through a multi-physics approach with both improved Point-Kinetics feedback model and spatial neutron kinetics. In particular, the Point Kinetics feedback model has been modified by modelling the void-effect non-linearity according to a parabolic interpolation of the results of Monte-Carlo neutron transport calculations. In practice, the Monte-Carlo code SERPENT was employed for the preparation of reactivity feedback parameters to be applied later to the Point Kinetics model of the thermal-hydraulic code TRACE.

The reactivity feedback coefficients are provided to TRACE by a set of SERPENT neutron transport calculations. The problem of strong non-linearity is tackled by building a new sodium density feedback model, where 8 zones are defined: five in the inner core region (lower blanket, inner fuel, inner blanket, upper fuel, plenum and above), three in the outer core region (lower blanket, inner fuel, plenum and above). In each zone, two coefficients, α_1 and α_2 are computed to model the parabolic interpolation of three simulation points: nominal case, sodium at 50% density and sodium voided. The sodium density reactivity is then computed as follows:

$$\rho_{Na} = \sum_{zones} [\alpha_2^{zone} (r_{perturbed}^{zone} - r_{nominal}^{zone})^2 + \alpha_1^{zone} (r_{perturbed}^{zone} - r_{nominal}^{zone})] \quad (1.6)$$

At each time step, TRACE evaluates the average sodium density in each of the eight zones. Sodium density reactivity feedback effect is then calculated according to (1.6).

Concerning the Doppler effect, feedback coefficients are evaluated for six fuel zones (upper fissile fuel, inner blanket, lower fissile fuel, lower blanket for the entire group of the inner fuel assemblies, and fissile fuel, fertile blanket for the entire group of the outer fuel assemblies) according to:

$$\rho_{Dop} = \sum_{zones} \alpha_{Dop}^{zone} \frac{\overline{\ln T_{perturbed}^{zone}}}{\overline{\ln T_{nominal}^{zone}}} \quad (1.7)$$

Doppler reactivity insertion is calculated with the same procedure as the sodium density feedback effect. A similar procedure is implemented for cladding expansion effect and control rod driveline expansion effect, which are evaluated linearly as a function of the average cladding temperature over the heat structure cells of the whole core and of the CR driveline average temperature, respectively.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1.5: (a) Core power and (b) total core inlet mass flow during ULOF accident in a CFV core simulated by the SERPENT-TRACE 1D approach.

The results obtained by the application of the above model to 1D TRACE simulation are shown in Figure 1.5 for 64 seconds of transient. During the simulated time (about 25 seconds of boiling) neither power rise nor permanent dryout are predicted, leading to consider the chance of a stabilized boiling regime during ULOF in a CFV core. A similar regime has been already simulated in previous studies, such as [7] and [8].

The main feature of the "stabilized boiling" regime is the strong oscillatory behaviour of the main physical quantities governing the ULOF transient. This behaviour can be explained by the presence of a dynamic thermal-hydraulic instability, which is characterized by a repeating process appearing as a cyclic steady-state. As stated in [8], the origin of this dynamic instability is not dependent on the neutronic void effect, but has been established to be hydraulic. The dynamic instability present in the transient corresponds to the chugging phenomenon [9]. However, in the literature other terms are sometimes used to refer to the same oscillatory phenomenon. In [10] and [11] the same phenomenology is referred as geysering and it is distinguished from the density wave oscillations possibly occurring in BWR.

Figure 1.6: Void fraction 1D axial profile along the hottest sub-assembly during ULOF accident in a CFV core simulated by the SERPENT-TRACE 1D approach.

In Figure 1.6 the void fraction 1D axial profile along the hottest sub-assembly is depicted. The void profile resembles the one presented in [8]: the boiling front stays confined at the top of the upper fissile zone while the lower fuel zones are filled by monophasic liquid. This explains the way the stabilized boiling regime allows to keep the fuel rods wetted without dryout occurring.

The chugging instability can be visually explained thanks to Figure 1.6. Sodium boiling is triggered at top of the fissile zone, where the margin to boiling is minimum. A slug of vapour promptly forms and abruptly grows both downwards, where it penetrates only few centimetres due to the natural circulation upward mass flow, and upwards, where it voids the sodium plenum.

At this point, the upper fissile zone and the sodium plenum are affected by a sizeable pressure drop due to the presence of the slug of vapour. Meanwhile, as the sodium vapour reaches the upper plenum, where

colder liquid sodium is present, it gets condensed. Consequently, the bubble collapse leads to a rapid liquid re-entering both from the core inlet and from the upper plenum, causing the two liquid fronts to bump into each other.

Figure 1.7: Pressure (above) and inlet mass flow rate (below) at the bottom of the hottest sub-assembly during ULOF accident in a CFV core simulated by the SERPENT-TRACE 1D approach.

This phenomenon is accompanied by pressure pulses, originating from the transformation of the kinetic energy of the two liquid fronts. The pressure pulses up to 30 bar propagate down the sub-assembly channel, as shown in Figure 1.7. The pressure peaks coincide with the occurrence of considerable dips in the sub-assembly inlet mass flow rate, corresponding to the instants of the collision between the two liquid fronts. This may highlight the presence of condensation induced sodium hammers.

Similar pressure peaks have already been measured in experimental facility with sodium. For example, in [12] pressure peaks up to 5-6 bar were measured in a sodium boiling experiment conducted in a 37-pin bundle under loss of flow conditions. The presence of the pressure peaks is thus physically and experimentally justified. However, the magnitude of the pressure pulses seems to be overestimated by TRACE due to the 1D modelisation, which can lead to what is known in thermal-hydraulics applications as water packing [13].

However, the presence of a "stabilized boiling" regime has profound implications with regards to safety. In addition to an enlarged grace time before boiling onset, the possibility not to have an abrupt power excursion and permanent dryout of the fuel rods during an extreme accident scenario as the ULOF case leads to classify the low-void core design as a new safety measure acting as a level of defence preventing the occurrence of severe accidents.

1.4 The chugging instability

As already highlighted in the previous section, a dynamic instability develops during the boiling phase of the ULOF transient in a SFR CFV core. Recalling that in [8] the same kind of instability has been simulated and analysed, the dynamic instability present in the transient has been identified to correspond to a **chugging phenomenon**.

The literature on the chugging instability is various and not always univocal. In [9], the chugging phenomenon is described as a periodic expulsion of the coolant out of a heating channel and composed of three main phases, as described in Figure 1.8:

1. *Incubation*: a slug of vapour forms between two columns of liquid and grows very rapidly;
2. *Expulsion*: the liquid is pushed out of the channel through the inlet and the outlet;
3. *Re-entering*: the fluid re-enters through the two ends of the channel.

Figure 1.8: Chugging phenomenon as described in [9]. 1,2,6: Incubation; 3,4: Expulsion; 6: Re-entering.

According to [14] a distinction is performed between chugging and *geysering* instabilities. The chugging phenomenon is referred as a dynamic instability occurring in pressure suppression pool systems and described in Figure 1.9. On the other hand, *geysering* is defined as quasi-static instability and occurs in systems as the one in Figure 1.10: the reservoir is filled with water which is heated up to the saturation temperature; once the water starts boiling the vapour bubbles rise up in the conduit causing a drop in the hydrostatic pressure that leads to flashing and ejection of water from the conduit; sub-cooled water then re-enters in the conduit and refills the reservoir.

As it may be noticed, the two latter phenomena are two aspects of the chugging instability described in [9]. This demonstrates the non-univocal terminology and direction with whom the study of this phenomenon is dealt. From now on, the dynamic instability under examination will be always referred simply as chugging.

The principal parameters governing the chugging instability are analyzed in [15] in the frame of startup transient in natural circulation loops (e.g. [16]). The driving mechanism of the periodic chugging phenomenon is explained as follows: voids are generated in a vertical heated channel when the liquid temperature equals the saturation temperature, leading to the formation of a large slug of bubbles. The dynamic formation of the slug of vapour causes a drop in the hydrostatic pressure term (ρgh) due to the difference of density between liquid and vapour. As a consequence, the slug of vapour grows and pushes the upper and lower columns of liquid. Once the vapour reaches the sub-cooled riser or the upper plenum, it mixes with the cold liquid and gets condensed. The subsequent bubble collapse brings about a sudden decrease in pressure that drives the liquid re-entering and restores the non-boiling condition. The periodic process then restarts once the liquid temperature reaches the saturation temperature and

Figure 1.9: Chugging phenomenon as described in [14].

Figure 1.10: Basic components for the geysering phenomenon as described in [14].

a new vapour slug forms.

From the description of the chugging phenomenology it is easy to define the parameters affecting mostly the instability behaviour:

- The **density ratio** ρ_g/ρ_l is crucial for the occurrence of the chugging phenomenon. The lower the ratio, the higher the pressure drop in case of void formation and consequently the faster the growth of the vapor slug pushing the columns of liquid out of the channel. For this reason the liquid metals as sodium are keen to this type of unstable behaviour.
- The **inlet subcooling** is fundamental for the development of the instability, since it determines the period and the amplitude of the oscillations: the consequence of lower inlet subcooling is an increase in the frequency and the amplitude of flow oscillations. This is explainable by the fact that, the liquid temperature being closer to the saturation temperature, it takes less time to be heated up to the formation of vapour, thus the oscillation period decreases. For the same reason, the speed of growth of the vapour slug is enhanced and consequently the amplitude of the oscillations is higher. On the other hand, if the subcooling is too high, the speed of growth of the vapour slug is not significant and its volume not important.
- The strength of the **heat source** influences the period and the amplitude of the oscillations similarly to the inlet subcooling. The stronger the heat source, the higher the frequency and the amplitude of the oscillations.
- The increase in **system pressure** has a stabilizing effect, since it reduces the possibility of the development of the instability. Pressure raises the saturation temperature and hinders the vapour generation, hampering the formation of large bubbles. This results in the damping of the oscillations and in general in a less oscillatory behaviour. This effect can be also explained by the decrease of the ratio ρ_g/ρ_l as pressure increases;
- The increase in **inlet mass flow rate** has a stabilizing effect. It enhances the heat transfer coefficient and allows to exchange heat without considerable temperature differences. Moreover, it hinders the formation of vapour slugs, resulting in a less oscillatory behaviour.

1.5 Direct Contact Condensation: literature review

In a previous work from the author [17], the presence of the chugging instability was calculated through simulations in support to the conceptual design development of a water test facility to mock up sodium boiling during Unprotected Loss Of Flow accidents. Thus, the chugging phenomenon occurring inside low-void effect SFR sub-assemblies may be reproduced by a water rig facility. The strong condensation induced pressure waves predicted by the analysis and the findings of the study is one of the main motivation for the construction of a test facility in the frame of the new Horizon-2020 ESFR-SMART project.

In the past a great multitude of experiments has been conducted to study the chugging regime in the frame of Direct Contact Condensation (DCC). DCC has grown interest since the 70s given that it is employed in the pressure suppression pools of Boiling Water Reactors (BWR) to reduce the containment pressure building up during LOCA by the vapour generated by the flashing of the water leaking from the damaged pipes [18]. In old and up-to-date BWR design the steam generated in the containment is indeed directed to the pressure suppression pool through a vent system. Since the pressure suppression pool is filled with water at high subcooling level, when the injected saturated steam comes in contact with it significantly high condensation heat transfer rate occurs, causing the steam to condense in very short time, from which the name Direct Contact Condensation.

However, as already explained in the previous section, the chugging dynamic instability may occur under specific conditions, generating strong pressure pulses that can damage the system. That is why a large number of scientific papers and experimental studies have been dedicated to the study of DCC and the possible regimes that may develop due to injection of steam into a subcooled water pool. The

conditions for the occurrence of chugging depend on three main parameters: the level of subcooling of the pool water; the steam injection flux; the diameter of the injection tube.

A list comprehensive of the main experimental studies on DCC and chugging instability in the frame of pressure suppression pools can be found in [19]. Plenty of researches focused their experiments on the development of condensation regime map for the description of the different patterns occurring during steam injection into subcooled liquid. For example, in [20] DCC is studied by injecting steam downwards into a pool of subcooled water and by recording the pattern developing at the steam-water interface. By varying the injection rate and the water pool subcooling the regime map shown in Figure 1.11 was obtained.

Figure 1.11: Condensation regime map for downward steam injection into subcooled water from [20].

In [21] the interest is more focused on the low injection rate region and on the development of a regime map for downward injection comprehensive of 4 main regimes with the corresponding typical pressure oscillation patterns (Figure 1.12):

- **Internal chugging**, occurring at small steam flux and low pool temperature and characterized by back-flow of pool water into vent tubes and largest pressure spikes with high frequency;
- **Small chugging**, characterized by the movement of the steam-water interface around the vent tube exit. The period of pressure oscillations is the same as the interval between the "chugs" of the high-frequency component of the previous case;
- **Condensation oscillation**, occurring at larger steam mass flux than chugging and characterized by the growth and shrinking of a steam bubble attached to the vent tube exit. Pressure oscillations are governed by the interface movement and thus occur with high frequency;
- **Bubbling**, occurring at high pool temperature and characterized by slow growth and detachment of the steam bubbles. The pressure oscillations show no high frequency component.

As shown from the map of Figure 1.12a, no pressure oscillation occurs at high pool temperature ($\sim 95^\circ\text{C}$), since the steam bubble is able to detach and reach the free water surface.

Figure 1.12: (a) Condensation regime map for downward steam injection into subcooled water and (b) corresponding typical pressure oscillation pattern at each regime from [21].

It must be pointed out that the previous regime map were obtained in case of atmospheric pressure and defined geometry. As already mentioned, the occurrence of the chugging phenomenon depends also on the diameter of the injection tube. Since the steam bubble generating at the vent tube exit gets its characteristic dimension from the diameter of the nozzle, the interface and thus the heat transfer are deeply influenced by the geometry of the experimental conditions. That is why in [22] a 3D condensation regime map including the vent diameter as additional parameter is developed by evaluating the experimental data from past studies.

However, the previously cited works focused on downward injection, typical of the BWR pressure suppression pool configuration. In [23] the case of upward injection of steam into subcooled water is also investigated. The major difference between upward and downward injection stands in the configuration of the interface at the chugging transition. While in case of downward injection the interface is relatively smooth and stable, the upward injection case shows a more wavy and fuzzy steam-water interface. This demonstrates that the product between the convection heat transfer and the interfacial area is higher in case of upward injection, resulting in an increased interface mixing and enhanced pressure oscillations. Consequently, in [23] the condensation regime map for upward injection visible in Figure 1.13 is proposed.

Figure 1.13: Condensation regime map for upward steam injection into subcooled water from [23].

The interface behaviour during chugging was deeply investigated in [24]. The outcome of this study is the discovery of the characteristic feature concerning the development of condensation induced pressure shocks: the formation of so-called "steam pockets" connected to the steam source through a "bottle-neck" (Figure 1.14).

At first, steam flows through the bottle-neck forming and expanding the steam pocket. This increases the interfacial area and thus the condensation rate. At the same time, the bottle-neck cross section decreases due to the unstable configuration of the steam pocket and consequently the steam velocity through the bottle-neck increases. This causes the formation of surface waves and the development of a Kelvin-Helmholtz-type instability on the steam-water interface. As a result, above a certain critical velocity in the bottle-neck, enhanced entrainment of atomized droplets occurs, leading abruptly to a strong

increase in the liquid-vapour interfacial area and in the condensation rate. The sudden condensation produces a depressurisation wave that sucks the liquid back into the injection tube and causes chugging. The generation of pressure pulses on the occurrence of sudden condensation of the steam bubble detached from the nozzle exit due to the necking phenomenon in case of horizontal injection was confirmed also by the experimental findings of [25].

Figure 1.14: Basic characteristic of "steam pocket" and "bottle-neck" during downward steam injection into subcooled pool as described by [24].

The amplitude and frequency of pressure oscillations were investigated at first in [26], that distinguished between chugging oscillations, occurring at low frequency and having strong violence, and condensation oscillations, with high frequency and limited amplitude. In [27] a theoretical linear stability analysis on these findings was conducted, indicating two main natural modes: the manometer mode of the liquid inside the end of the vent, characteristic of chugging oscillations; the first acoustic mode, characteristic of condensation oscillations.

In [28] the Froude number was identified as decisive parameter for the representation of a scaled non-dimensional amplitude and frequency. The scaled amplitude is found to have a maximum at $Fr \sim 2.8$ while the scaled frequency a minimum at $Fr \sim 6$.

Another important feature of steam injection into a subcooled pool of water is the development of thermal stratification, which may result decisive in the condensation heat transfer characteristics over time. The thermal stratification is influenced by the steam injection according to two sources: a localized heat source due to the direct contact condensation and a localized momentum source due to the velocity of steam forced into the vent. In [29] it is found that a definite thermal stratification occurs for low steam mass fluxes, while no thermal stratification is visible at large steam mass fluxes. This means that high steam injection velocities induce turbulence and penetration of the heat source throughout the whole axial extent, leading the water pool thermal stratification to disappear. However, in case of chugging, where low steam mass flux is employed, the thermal stratification is significantly detectable due to the strong condensation processes occurring at the vent tube exit.

It is important to point out that 1D thermal-hydraulics codes showed deficiency in the prediction of thermal stratification in the pool in case of steam injection. For example, the analysis conducted in [30] highlighted that, while complete mixing was predicted using TRACE, thermal stratification was observed in the experiment. That is why new models (e.g. [31]) have been recently developed in order to predict more accurately thermal stratification and mixing.

1.6 Goals of Thesis: the CHUG experiment

One of the main aims of the ESFR-SMART European project is the production of new experimental data in order to support calibration and validation of the computational tools for each defence-in-depth level.

The state-of-the-art in the area of the chugging regime of the sodium boiling is very limited and very limited number of corresponding experiments were performed, one of which based on using water as sodium simulant [32].

In the frame of ESFR-SMART, in order to better understand and simulate the chugging boiling regime condition and to gather new experimental data, a new simple facility called CHUG was planned to be designed and built using water as sodium simulant. The main purpose of this Master's Thesis has been the design and realisation of the experimental facility "CHUG" for the mock-up of sodium boiling in Sodium-cooled Fast Reactor assemblies. This has also included the conduction of the first tests and the comparison between the experimental data and the results from simulations performed with thermal-hydraulics code TRACE and PSI's in-house CFD code (PSI-BOIL).

Despite the pre-conceptual design study performed in the Semester Project of the author [17] envisaged a geometry resembling a low-void SFR sub-assembly, the design has been simplified for the sake of the simplicity of the configuration.

CHUG test section has been designed as a vertical pipe of few-centimetre diameter composed of two elements connected by flanges. During the first stage of the experimental tests, both the elements have been planned to be made of stainless steel. The test section is filled with light water at 20°C at atmospheric pressure. High-pressure steam produced by a commercial steam generator is injected from the lower part of the test section under conditions aiming to simulate sodium boiling behaviour using water as a simulant. The interaction between the injected steam and cold water has been analysed to study the conditions of the chugging boiling regime occurrence and condensation-induced pressure waves. For this purpose, a piezoelectric pressure sensor has been installed at the bottom of the test facility to track the fast pressure changes caused by steam condensation. Moreover, thermocouples have been installed along the test section to track the increase of water temperature due to the high-pressure steam injection.

At a future stage of the experimental tests, the upper stainless steel section will be replaced by an analogous acrylic glass element, that will allow to record the steam bubbles behaviour during condensation inside the facility through the use of a high-speed camera.

In parallel, analytical simulations of the experiment were conducted at PSI by the use of the thermal-hydraulics code TRACE to assess the validity of the code for the simulation of chugging boiling. Moreover, the behaviour of high-pressure steam bubbles in cold water was investigated through the CFD code PSI-BOIL in order to compare the code prediction with the actual experimental visualization performed by the high-speed camera. Additionally, by implementing sodium properties into PSI-BOIL, the behaviour of sodium and water bubbles was compared to assess the suitability of water as sodium simulant.

In brief, the major goals of this Master's Thesis project and of the overall CHUG project can be summarized in:

- Contribution to the experimental knowledge about the chugging boiling regime, whose state-of-the-art area is limited.

- Analysis of the conditions of the occurrence of the chugging boiling regime and of condensation-induced pressure waves.
- Assessment of the validity of the thermal-hydraulics codes for the chugging sodium boiling, to be used in the future ESFR-SMART core to simulate the ULOF conditions.
- Preparation for the comparison of the results obtained by the CFD simulation performed by the state-of-the-art code PSI-BOIL with the experimental data, in order to assess the quality of the code predictions and to obtain data for a future comparison with the case where sodium is employed.

The structure of this Thesis can be outlined as follows. Firstly, an overview of the experimental setup will be presented. Secondly the results from pre-calculations performed with TRACE and PSI-BOIL are highlighted. Finally, the results from the experimental tests will be presented and discussed.

Chapter 2

CHUG: Experimental setup

As already mentioned in Section 1.6, the major aim of the CHUG experimental facility is the provision of new experimental data regarding the chugging phenomenon for the validation of thermal-hydraulic codes to be employed for SFR safety simulations.

During this Master’s Thesis, the principal endeavour consisted of planning the overall CHUG project, with particular focus on the design and setup of the experimental facility and the conduction of the first experimental test to prove the feasibility and the potential of the project.

The main challenge consisted of planning the reproduction of a complex instability phenomenon while at the same time keeping the design as simple as possible, due to budget and time constraints. At the first stage of this Thesis work, several suppliers were contacted for the acquisition of the instrumentation and of the test section. The materials and the instrumentation chosen and presented in this Chapter were selected according to the actual needs of the chugging phenomenon representation and measurement, always accounting for the budget constraint.

Figure 2.1: Gantt chart for the Master’s Thesis project.

Moreover, the plan of time schedule revealed to be a challenging task, due to the time constraint given by the nature and time-frame of the Master’s Thesis itself. The Gantt Chart displayed in Figure 2.1 shows the Master’s Thesis work as initially planned and as actually performed.

In the following Sections, the experimental setup is presented along with a close insight on each component utilised for the experiment. Particular attention has been given to the LabVIEW data acquisition system program developed and tailored for the CHUG facility.

2.1 Experimental apparatus

The scheme of CHUG experimental setup is depicted in Figure 2.2. The test section consists of a 2.2 m high and 5 cm inner diameter pipe filled with water at room temperature, where high-pressure steam is injected into through a dedicated steam line.

Figure 2.2: Scheme of CHUG experimental setup.

The steam line also serves as discharge line, for refill and discharge operations regarding the subcooled water inside the test section. The steam is provided to the system by a commercial steam generator, which employs service water for the generation of steam at 6-7 bar.

The measurement system consists of one piezoelectric pressure sensor screwed at the bottom of the test section and three thermocouples fixed on the test section wall at three different axial positions ($h = 25\text{cm}, 70\text{cm}, 120\text{cm}$) and penetrating horizontally until the centre of the tube cross section. All of these sensors are connected to the data acquisition system, which is in turn connected to a PC for the analysis of data.

The test section is maintained in fixed vertical position at approximately 1 m from the soil thanks to a metal frame, which is fixed mechanically to the ground. A shielding surrounds the test section in

order to protect the electronic devices of the acquisition system. Pictures of the CHUG experimental facility can be visualized in Figure 2.3.

The experimental procedure is carried out as follows. Distilled water is injected into the test section until the set-point (equal to a height of 1.8 m) defined by the use of a floater. When the test section is filled with water, the steam generator is turned on.

In the first stage, the injection line is kept closed while the water discharge line is opened damping the steam outside. This allows measuring the steam temperature at the steam generator outlet and at the test section inlet through the use of portable thermocouples. Also, this way the steam line tube is heated up, minimizing the losses of heat from the flowing steam to the surrounding environment. When the steam temperature measurements are taken and the steam line is heated up, the discharge water line valve is closed and the injection line is opened in order to start the test. The test time length is limited by the working temperature of the pressure sensor: when the water surrounding the injection nozzle reaches around 100°C the test must be stopped, since a further increase in water temperature can endanger the pressure sensor. At this point, the injection line is closed and the water discharge line is reopened in order to damp the remaining steam from the steam generator, which is turned off. When no more steam to damp is left, the test section is voided by opening together the injection line and water discharge line valves and by closing the steam generator outlet valve.

It must be pointed out that the test section gets significantly heated up during the tests. It is thus necessary to continuously injecting and discharging fresh water for several minutes in order to bring back the steel section to room temperature and start a new test. Throughout the whole procedure, the readings from the pressure sensor and the thermocouples are tracked by the acquisition system and saved into TDMS files, which are later post-processed by MATLAB.

In order to investigate the capabilities of the experimental apparatus, the main characteristics of each of the components of the experimental apparatus is described below.

2.1.1 Test section

The test section designed for the first phase of the CHUG project has been chosen with a basic design for the sake of simplicity. It consists of two stainless steel flanged tubes fastened to each other through the use of bolts. The inner diameter of both tubes is equal to 5 cm while the outer diameter is equal to 6 cm, resulting in a tube thickness of 0.5 cm. The flanges have been obtained by the manufacture of a rim at the end of both tubes with axial thickness equal to 1 cm and diameter equal to 240 cm. Six holes are screwed around the rim at 100 cm distance from the center of the tube in order to allow the fastening by bolts.

The two pieces differ in axial dimensions and features as it follows:

- The lower part of the test section consists of a 0.2 meter flanged tube. The lower rim allows the connection of a stainless steel cover disc with the same diameter of the flange and 2 cm height hosting the holes for the connection of the pressure sensor (screwed) and the steam injection pipe. The upper rim is connected to the upper part of the test section.
- The upper part of the test section consists of a 2 meter flanged tube. The lower rim is connected to the lower part of the test section while the upper rim is left unfastened and represents the top of the test section. Along the axial walls, three horizontal holes have been bored for the fastening of the three thermocouples envisaged for the temperature measurement.

More details about the mechanical configuration of the two parts of the test section and the cover disc can be found in the drawings of Figure 2.4. It must be pointed out that the fastening of all the flanges is obtained through the use of sealing Teflon discs.

Figure 2.3: Pictures displaying the CHUG facility as it appears in the EPFL's Laboratory of Reactor Physics and Systems Behaviour.

The steam line consists of a pipe made of stainless steel with inner and outer diameter equal to 6 mm and 8 mm, respectively. In order to minimize the heat losses when steam is flowing, the whole steam line has been surrounded by a layer of thermal insulator.

Figure 2.5: Lower part of the test section connected to the cover disc at the bottom along with the inner steam injection tube.

A picture of the lower part of the test section is displayed in Figure 2.5 along with the part of the injection tube already fixed inside it. It must be noticed that the injection tube is bent inside the test section in order to achieve steam injection exactly at the centre of the cross section. The hole for the injection line is indeed placed 17 mm away from the center of the cover disc.

The connection through flanges has the important advantage in the capability of replacing the upper part of the test section with an acrylic glass part for the future stage of the experiment, as well as to implement revised geometries as in [17] in future by simply connecting new manufactured pieces.

The test section is fixed in vertical position at around 1 meter from the soil thanks to the use of a metal frame. In order to reduce oscillations of the structure due to the pressure oscillations developing during the experiment, the frame is in turn fixed to a concrete wall and two blocks of concrete are placed at the level of the fastening flanges in order to increase the inertia of the structure. Vibrations of the structure can indeed affect the readings performed by the pressure sensor and must be minimised.

2.1.2 Steam generator

The steam generator selected for the first stage of the CHUG project is the *TEKNIK K-DH-6kW* steam boiler from *AB&Co* (Figure 2.6). As it is visible from Table 2.1, where the technical data are shown, the variable range of steam output and working pressure as well as the small weight and volume lead to the choice of this steam boiler.

Figure 2.6: AB&Co TEKNIK K-DH-6kW steam boiler used in CHUG experiment.

Table 2.1: Technical data of AB&Co TEKNIK K-DH-6kW steam boiler.

Technical Specifications	Value	Units
Max. Power	6	kW
Working Pressure	2 - 6	bar gauge
Design Pressure	7	bar gauge
Steam Output	3 - 9	kg/h
Voltage	400	V
Volume of boiler compartments	4.9	l
Min. Water Level Volume	2	l
Pump motor	0.37	kW
Steam Outlet Dimension	3/8"	
Feed Water Inlet Dimension	3/8"	
Overall Size of Cabinet L x W x H	390 x 550 x 1000	mm
Net Weight	57	kg

Figure 2.7 displays all the boiler components, specified in Table 2.2. The inlet water is pumped into the boiler shell through a 0.37kW-pump until a level set by the level control. Then the water is heated up by an electrical heater building up pressure inside the boiling shell. Pressure is monitored by a pressure gauge and it is constrained by a safety valve, which switches off the heater as soon as the pressure reaches the selected set-point. When the steam valve is opened, the steam flows out of the boiler shell and can be provided to the steam line. When the level of water in the boiler shell is lowered, the pump is brought back in function and new water is supplied for heating.

It must be pointed out that the steam generator tends to lose pressure when the valve is opened. By selecting the correct aperture of the valve the pressure can be stabilized by reaching an equilibrium between the pressure build-up due to vapour generation and the pressure decrease due to steam outflow.

Figure 2.7: AB&Co TEKNIK K-DH-6kW steam boiler components.

Table 2.2: Components of AB&Co TEKNIK K-DH-6kW steam boiler.

Pos.	Description
1	Socket for iron connection
2	Water inlet
7	Upper panel
9	Steam valve
10	Safety valve Up to 7 bar
11	Pressure gauge 0-10 bar
12	Check valve
13	Solenoid valve, Complete 230V 50/60Hz
14	Blow down valve
15	Hose holder 12
16	Water filter
17	Pump - 8,5 bar - 230V - 50Hz
18	Name plate
19	Protective cover for heaters
20	Lower panel
21	Square rubber foot
23	Pressure switch 2 - 5,5 bar
24	Level control gasket 135X82
25	Heating Battery
26	Level control, Complete automatic with micro switch 43D013
27	Boiler shell

2.1.3 Data acquisition system

Data acquisition (DAQ) consists of measuring an electrical signal such as voltage or current generated by a physical phenomenon, which can involve e.g. temperature, pressure or sound. PC-based data

acquisition uses a combination of modular hardware, application software and a computer to make data from measurements available for collection, visualization or further post-processing.

The DAQ system is composed of three main parts (Figure 2.8):

1. **Sensor**, also called transducer, which converts a physical phenomenon into a measurable electrical signal. Depending on the type of sensor, its electrical output can be a voltage, current, resistance or another electrical quantity varying over time;
2. **Hardware** acting as the interface between a computer and signals acquired from the sensor. Its main function is the digitalization of incoming analog signals to make them available for the computer to read them. The three key components of a DAQ device employed for signal measurement are the signal conditioning circuitry, analog-to-digital converter (ADC) and computer bus.
3. **Software**, which controls the operation of the hardware and processes, visualizes, stores measurement data. The software is made of two main components: the Driver software and the Application software.

The first provides application software the ability to interact with the hardware by abstracting low-level hardware commands and register-level programming. Typically, a driver software exposes an application programming interface (API) that is used within a programming environment to build application software.

On the other hand, the Application software manages the interaction between the computer and user. It can be either a pre-built application with predefined functionality or a programming environment for building applications with custom functionality.

Figure 2.8: Data acquisition structure scheme.

Usually the signals generated in the sensors have too much noise to be measured directly. That is why **Signal Conditioning** is fundamental in order to make the signals readable by the hardware. Signal conditioning is defined as the process of preparation of a signal with the purpose of making it suitable for the ADC. Signal is manipulated by a circuitry that can include amplification, attenuation, filtering and isolation.

Signal conditioning can occur in the sensor itself, along the path between the sensor and the hardware through external amplifiers and filters and directly in the DAQ hardware. In the latter case two main components are responsible of the communication to the driver software:

- the Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) which converts the analog signals from the sensor into digital in order to enable the manipulation by digital equipment such as a computer. ADC consists of a chip providing digital representation of analog signals at any instant in time, by taking periodic samples at a predefined rate;
- the Computer Bus, which transfers the digital signals from the ADC to the computer where the original signal is reconstructed from the samples. The connection between the DAQ hardware and the computer is enabled by a slot or port.

In CHUG experiment, the data acquisition system has been entirely provided by *National Instruments* (NI). In particular the CHUG DAQ system is based on the NI CompactDAQ platform *cDAQ9174* (Figure 2.9a) where two modules are plugged: *NI-9211* (Figure 2.9b) for thermocouples measurement and *NI-9250* (Figure 2.9c) for IEPE sensor measurement. The CompactDAQ platform is connected to the computer through an USB bus. The data acquisition specifications are displayed in Table 2.3 while the data acquisition structure is depicted in Figure 2.10.

Table 2.3: Technical data of data acquisition system.

cDAQ-9174	Value	Units
Slot Count	4	
Timing Accuracy	50	ppm of sample rate
Timing Resolution	12.5	ns
NI-9211	Value	Units
Max. Nr. of Analog Inputs	4	
Maximum Sample Rate	14	S/s
Analog Input Isolation	250	Vrms
Measurement Accuracy	0.92	°C
NI-9250	Value	Units
Max. Nr. of Analog Inputs	2	
Maximum Sample Rate	102.4	kS/s/ch
Analog Input Voltage Range	-5 to 5	V
IEPE Excitation	2	mA

Pressure sensor

The choice of the pressure sensor is crucial for the success of the CHUG experiment. In order to measure the oscillatory behaviour typical of chugging instability, it is fundamental to be able to detect the pressure pulses due to bubble collapse. For this purpose the sensor must be able to have the sufficient high-frequency response to the fast pressure rises. Moreover, since the predictions of the calculations on the magnitude of these pressure peaks are variable, the pressure sensor must have the proper range of measurement. All these criteria have obviously to be met along with the budget constraint.

In order to fulfil all the requirements listed above the attention was directed to piezoelectric pressure sensors for the measurement of dynamic pressure.

This type of pressure sensors is based on the **piezoelectric effect**, which denotes the ability of ceramic or quartz crystals to generate electric voltage as they experience compressive stresses. Piezoelectric pressure sensors contain a seismic mass directly applying forces on the surrounding crystal in response to the applied dynamic pressure: this generates a high-impedance, electrical charge proportional to the applied force, which is converted into low-impedance voltage through an amplifier.

The amplifier could be external, as in *Charge Output Sensors*, or included in built-in integrated circuits as in case of *Internally Amplified Sensors*. In this study only the latter case has been taken into account.

Internally Amplified Sensors are commonly called **IEPE** (Integrated Electronic Piezoelectric Accelerometers). They are composed of a built-in charge-sensitive amplifier: according to the charge generated on the piezoelectric crystal, this amplifier varies its impedance while accepting a constant direct current (DC) source. The change in impedance can be measured as a change in voltage across the inputs of the sensor. A typical IEPE Quartz Pressure Sensor is displayed in Figure 2.11.

A typical sensor system including a quartz IEPE sensor, ordinary two-conductor cable and basic constant current signal conditioner is shown in Figure 2.12. The signal conditioner in exam consists of a regulated 24 VDC source, a current-regulating diode and a capacitor for decoupling the signal (AC coupling to remove the DC offset created by the excitation current), as well as a voltmeter monitoring the sensor bias voltage.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2.9: Components of data acquisition system used in CHUG experiment: (a) CompactDAQ chassis; (b) module for thermocouples measurement; (c) module for IEPE sensor measurement.

Figure 2.10: Data acquisition structure as in CHUG.

Figure 2.11: Cross section of a typical quartz pressure sensor with built-in electronics.

The pressure sensor chosen for CHUG task is the *PCB PIEZOTRONICS* model 113B24 (Figure 2.13). It consists of a piezoelectric, quartz pressure sensor for dynamic pressure measurement. The instrument specifications are presented in Table 2.4.

As it is noticeable, this model of piezoelectric pressure sensor is able to detect fast pressure pulses with good sensitivity and resolution. In particular, applying the Nyquist Theorem, this device is able to adequately sample pulses occurring with frequency equal to:

$$f_N = \frac{f_{\text{sampling}}}{2} = \frac{500\text{kHz}}{2} = 250\text{kHz} \quad (2.1)$$

which is largely sufficient for the expected needs of CHUG experiment.

Figure 2.12: Typical IEPE sensor system.

Figure 2.13: *PCB* pressure sensor model 113B24 used in CHUG facility.

Table 2.4: Technical specifications of *PCB* pressure sensor model 113B24 used in CHUG facility.

Technical Specifications	Value	Units
Measurement Range ($\pm 5V$)	6895	kPa
Useful Overrange ($\pm 10V$)	13790	kPa
Sensitivity	0.725	mV/kPa
Maximum Pressure	68950	kPa
Voltage	400	V
Resolution	0.035	kPa
Resonant Frequency	≥ 500	kHz
Rise Time (Reflected)	1	μs
Low Frequency response (-5%)	0.005	Hz
Non-Linearity	$\leq 1\%$	
Temperature Range	-73..135	$^{\circ}C$
Discharge Time Constant	≥ 100	s
Electrical Connector	10-32	Coaxial Jack

Thermocouples

The three thermocouples employed in the first phase of the CHUG experiment have been chosen with the purpose of tracking the thermal stratification at three different axial position. That is why no special

design was requested for the choice of these sensors.

Thermocouples employ the thermoelectric effect for the measurement of temperature: two wires of different materials connected through a junction produce a voltage at their free ends if the junction is at different temperature with respect to the free ends. This is due to a property of conductive materials that adjust their electronic density according to temperature gradient, becoming a voltage source on their own. If two different materials are chosen for the connected wires, different voltage is generated along the two different wires and this results in a voltage difference at the free ends. This enables the continuous measurement of the temperature at the junction by tracking the generated voltage signal at the free ends.

The thermocouples chosen for the CHUG project are mineral-insulated NiCr-Ni K-type thermocouple provided by *MTS Messtechnik Schaffhausen GmbH* and displayed in Figure 2.14. The diameter of the mineral-coated junction is 1.5 mm. The small diameter allows the insertion inside the test section without any sensible modification of the flow conditions inside the test section.

Figure 2.14: Mineral-insulated K-type thermocouple used in CHUG facility.

It must be mentioned that the thermocouple is screwed into the test section thanks to the use of a compression socket that is applied to the thermocouple through a seal ring and permits an easy and stable fixation of the sensor during the experimental tests.

2.1.4 Data acquisition software

As already explained in previous section, the DAQ software installed in the computer controls the data acquisition operations, processes and stores the data transmitted by the hardware. In particular, the Application software acts as the interface between the user and the acquisition system. During this Master's Thesis the Laboratory Virtual Instrument Engineering Workbench (LabVIEW) has been utilized for the programming of the data acquisition.

LabVIEW is a graphical programming environment distributed by *National Instruments* and used for data acquisition, instrument control and industrial automation. LabVIEW represents a platform-based approach for measurement and control being able to play the role of interface with a wide variety of hardware.

The main characteristics of LabVIEW can be summarized in:

- **Graphical:** LabVIEW uses icons and wires instead of text. It enables the creation of front panels where subroutines called virtual instruments (VIs) run for the acquisition of control of devices.

- **Dataflow-oriented:** the data availability between nodes in the code determines the execution order. If there is enough data available to a function, the latter is executed.

LabVIEW is based on the execution of Virtual Instruments (VIs). Each VI has three components: a block diagram, a front panel and a connector panel. The last is used to represent the VI in the block diagrams of other, calling VIs. Controls and indicators on the front panel allow the user to input or output data during the execution of a VI. The block diagram contains the graphical source code.

Each object dropped in the front panel has its correspondent in the block diagram, which contains also functions performing operations on controls and supply data to indicators. In general, controls, indicators and functions are named nodes, which are connected through wires.

The execution order of the program is dependent on the structure of the block diagram, i.e. on the connection between the nodes. The data are propagated through the wires and a node can execute only in case all the inputs are available.

For the acquisition of measurements, LabVIEW uses DAQ software to control the hardware by sending and receiving signal information. Moreover, LabVIEW is able to specify when and from which channels to acquire data. In simple terms, LabVIEW selects a physical channel (i.e. the terminal or pin at which signal can be measured) and encapsulates it with other channel specific information through a virtual channel. A set of virtual channels along with their properties is named task, which represents the measurement or generation to be performed.

LabVIEW includes several tools for the connection to the DAQ device. In this study, the DAQ program utilised for CHUG experiment has been realized through the use of the so called "NI-DAQmx API". It consists of several functions (VIs) that control the hardware with fine options to optimize the performance of the overall acquisition process. The acquisition application generated with DAQmx VIs allows the measurement data to be accessible from any other application.

A basic DAQmx application involves the following VIs:

- **DAQmx Create Virtual Channel VI** creates a virtual channel and adds it to a task, allowing the configuration of the data acquisition settings;
- **DAQmx Timing VI** configures the timing for hardware-timed data acquisition operations. Namely it defines whether the operation is continuous or finite, the number of samples to acquire, the buffer and the type of clock used for the acquisition;
- **DAQmx Trigger VI** configures the triggering of a specific action. Triggering starts or stops a task according to rising or falling digital or analog edges.
- **DAQmx Start Task VI** initiates the task after its configuration;
- **DAQmx Read VI** acquires data from a DAQ device;
- **DAQmx Stop Task VI** halts the task and returns it to the state before the start operation;
- **DAQmx Clear Task VI** releases all the resources the task reserved;
- **Simple Error Handler VI** checks for errors during the data acquisition and responds to them.

The data acquisition application customized for CHUG task uses buffered data transfer for continuous acquisition. When reaching the hardware, the analog signal passes through the instrumentation amplifier to the ADC. During buffered acquisition the signal is transferred to an on-board First In First Out (FIFO) buffer which stores the data until they can be transferred from the device to the computer. The data transfer from the hardware to the PC buffer occurs through Direct Memory Access (DMA). The PC buffer is a memory location storing the data after leaving the device and is configured by the number of samples per channel input. The data are read continuously from the software until the loop for continuous acquisition stops.

The data acquisition performed in CHUG experiment is hardware-timed, namely the rate of acquisition is controlled by a hardware signal such as the sample clock, which controls the time interval between

samples. A hardware clock is usually faster than a software loop, thus a higher range of frequencies can be sampled without aliasing the signal. Moreover, a hardware clock is more accurate than a software loop and not susceptible to distractions such as share of RAM usage.

During CHUG experiment a further degree of complexity is added due to the presence of signals processed by different modules: NI-9250 for the piezoelectric pressure measurement and NI-9211 for thermocouples measurement. In this case it is necessary to create multidevice tasks.

Channel expansion is one of the possible method to be implemented. It is the process of expanding the channels of a data acquisition device to include channels of another device, effectively creating a single task with more channels. This method has the benefit of automatic synchronization, i.e. DAQmx automatically routes triggers and clocks at driver level so that the multiple devices are synchronized. In other words, this type of synchronization makes the devices function as one.

However, this method can be applied only to signals of the same type. Thus, in the case of study, only the three signals coming from the three thermocouples can be routed into the same task. On the other hand, the different nature of the pressure signal forces the creation of a new task.

Therefore, two tasks running in parallel inside the same loop are envisaged in order to acquire simultaneously pressure and temperature data. Since hardware timing is used, the initiation of the task as well triggers the acquisition of the samples. The problem rises when two independent tasks are present. Due to the dataflow characterization of LabVIEW the two **DAQmx Start Task VIs**, even if they begin at the same relative time, they will have a different exact start times and their separation is determined by the software time delay between the executions of the two VIs, controlled by the operating system. In such type of cases the synchronization is essential, since it allows to coordinate and relate the signals to each other. In order to achieve synchronization a precise shared trigger along with coordination of the tasks has been implemented.

First of all, it must be pointed out that without any trigger specification the **DAQmx Start Task VI** uses a default trigger for analog input, named **ai/StartTrigger**. In order to synchronize the two tasks, they must share the same trigger. With this purpose a **Master and Slave** architecture must be built. In this study the task representing the pressure signal is the master while the one representing temperature signals is the slave. The master task is initiated simply without any trigger setup, thus using the default **ai/StartTrigger**. On the other hand, the slave task is configured to start when the internal trigger (**ai/StartTrigger**) is asserted. Moreover, the start of the slave task must be executed before the start of the master task. This way the slave task is ready to be triggered as soon as the master task gets started.

However, a shared trigger might not be enough to keep measurements synchronized because of the following types of timing errors:

- *Skew*, which is the propagation delay caused when a signal arrives at two places at different times. It is affected by distance and impedance of signal paths;
- *Jitter*, namely the small variations in the period of a clock from sample to sample;
- *Stability*, describing how well the clock frequency resists fluctuations due e.g. to temperature or aging;
- *Drift*, occurring when two instruments acquire data at different sample rates even though set to acquire for the same sample rate. Even identical clocks have indeed small variances in frequency that cause the clocks to drift apart over time.

In order to solve the timing errors caused by the shared trigger, the simplest way to synchronize measurements and avoid drift is to make the two tasks share the same Sample Clock. Thus the slave timing settings are modified to be governed by the same Sample Clock as the master task. The data acquired are continuously displayed in two waveform graphs keeping track of the trend of pressure and temperature over time. The data acquisition program as visualized in LabVIEW is presented in Figure 2.15.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.15: Data acquisition program tailored for the CHUG experimental tests as visualized in LabVIEW.

Chapter 3

TRACE pre-calculations

Pre-calculations realized with US NRC TRACE code were performed both in support of both the design phase and the decision-making process for the acquisition of instruments and material for the experimental setup.

Furthermore, TRACE pre-calculations play the role of assessing the validity of this thermal-hydraulics code in the accurate simulation of the chugging phenomenon calculated for the ULOF transient scenario in SFR sub-assemblies.

A model based on the final experimental setup was built and used for the simulation of the experimental conditions. In this section, a brief overview of the US NRC TRACE code is given, followed by the presentation of the model utilised in the calculations. The results are then presented and discussed along with several sensitivity studies to assess the influence of various the model features.

3.1 TRACE

TRACE is a thermal-hydraulics system code developed by US NRC with the aim of performing best-estimate analyses of operational transients and accident scenarios occurring in light water reactors [33]. Models have however been introduced to render TRACE capable of analysing Sodium-cooled Fast Reactors and enabling the simulation of sodium boiling, as for example in [34]. TRACE can be used even for the modelisation of thermal-hydraulic phenomena occurring in experimental facilities (such as CHUG) designed for the reproduction of transients in reactor systems.

TRACE solves a six-equation full two-fluid hydrodynamic model to describe two-phase flow and heat transfer. The partial differential equations are solved using a finite volume numerical methods by employing a multi-step time-differencing procedure for the resolution of the fluid-dynamics equations and a semi-implicit time-differencing technique for the heat equations. The finite difference equations for hydrodynamic phenomena form a system of coupled, non-linear equations that are solved by the Newton-Raphson iteration method. The resulting linearised equations are solved by direct matrix inversion.

This allows important phenomena to be simulated explicitly. Examples are counter-current flow, multi-dimensional flow patterns in the reactor-core and plenum regions, wall friction losses, critical flow and water-hammer.

TRACE employs a component-based approach for the modelling of a system. A flow loop can be represented as an aggregation of components, which can be further nodalised into a number of cells, consisting of physical volumes over which the fluid and conduction equations are averaged. Components for the modelling of fuel elements or heated walls, called heat structures, are available for the computation of two-dimensional conduction and surface-convection heat transfer.

More details on TRACE algorithm and models can be found in [33].

3.2 CHUG 2D TRACE model

In this section the 2D TRACE model will be shortly outlined. The 2D TRACE model to simulate the behaviour of CHUG experiment has been built with the help of the Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package (SNAP), which consists of a suite of integrated applications designed to simplify the process of performing engineering analysis. SNAP provides a highly flexible framework for creating and editing input for engineering analysis codes, such as e.g. TRACE [35].

In Figure 3.1 the 2D TRACE model for CHUG facility as appearing from the Model Editor of SNAP is presented. The 2D model is composed of 10 components:

- a FILL component (nr. 100) represents the Steam Generator. In base-case calculation the FILL component is set to inject constantly 1 g/s of high-pressure steam (at 5 bar pressure and 425 K temperature) starting at 10 s with a linear ramp-up of 1 s. The volume of this component is chosen sufficiently big in order not to influence the flow in the injection tube.
- a VALVE component (nr. 10) represents the injection tube. In base-case calculation this component plays the role of a pipe, whose length is 1.55 m and which is characterized by an elbow bend to simulate the actual conditions of the experiment. A VALVE component instead of a PIPE was chosen in order to be able in future to regulate the inflow of steam. The cells composing the pipe are more refined close to the injection point in order to attempt to capture the phenomena involving the steam-water interface during the injection.
- a VESSEL component (nr. 1) plays the role of the test section. This is the only 3D component of the current model and gives the 2D characterization. The base-case VESSEL is composed of 50 axial levels, 3 radial rings and only 1 azimuthal node. The axial height of the cells is chosen as equal to the hydraulic diameter of the test section while the radial rings are modelled in order to obtain approximately the same volume for each cell of the component. The VESSEL is modelled to have 2.5 height and 0.5 m elevation from the ground and to be initially filled with a 2-meter column of water at atmospheric pressure and ambient temperature (20°C). The remaining 0.5 m column at the top of the test section is filled with air at ambient temperature. The steam injection is obtained by connecting the VALVE component to the central cell at the 5th level (at a height of 25 cm).
- a Heat Structure (nr. 40) models the heat transfer between the test section and the surrounding environment. In order to simulate the presence of air at the outer surface of the test section, the outer surface temperature was set to be constant and equal to 20°C. The material of the heat structure consists of stainless steel type 304.
- 3 BREAK components (nr. 20, 21, 22), one for each VESSEL radial ring, are connected to the top of the test section component. These components are needed to simulate the top opening of the test section to the surrounding air, thus the boundary condition are set to be atmospheric pressure and ambient temperature.
- 3 Single Junctions components (nr. 30, 31, 32) which serve as connection between the BREAK components and the VESSEL.

The parameters of the 2D CHUG TRACE model are summarized in Table 3.1.

Figure 3.1: 2D TRACE model as appearing from SNAP's Model Editor.

TRACE components data		
Component	Parameter	Value
FILL	Vapour Temperature	425 K
	Pressure	5 bar
	Vapour Mass Flow Rate	1 g/s
VALVE	Nr. of cells	10
	Length	1.55 m
	Hydraulic Diameter	5 mm
	Initial void fraction	0.0
	Initial Temperature	293 K
	Initial Pressure	1 bar
VESSEL	Axial levels	50
	Total Height	2.5 m
	Height of single cell	5 cm
	Radial rings	3
	Hydraulic diameter	5 cm
	Position of radial nodes	1.4-2-2.5 cm
	Azimuthal nodes	1
	Initial water level	2.0 m
	Initial Temperature	293 K
	Initial Pressure	1 bar
	Height of Injection point	25 cm
	Elevation	0.5 m
HEATSTR	Material	Stainless steel (type 301)
	Axial levels	50
	Total Height	2.5 m
	Height of single cell	5 cm
	Radial nodes	3
	Thickness	0.5 cm
	Outer surface temperature	293 K
BREAK	Temperature	293 K
	Pressure	1 bar

Table 3.1: Simulation parameters of the 2D TRACE model for the CHUG facility.

3.3 Base-case calculation

In this section the results from base-case calculation performed with the thermal-hydraulics code TRACE are presented. As already mentioned in the previous section, the base-case consists of a constant injection of high-pressure steam starting at 10 seconds with a 1-second ramp-up. The injection ceases at 58 seconds, when the injection mass flow rate decreases linearly to zero until 59 seconds. The total simulation time is equal to 60 seconds. The steam mass flow rate in the injection pipe is depicted in the plot of Figure 3.2a.

The conditions of this calculation aim to reproduce the actual conditions occurring during experimental tests. In Figure 3.2b the pressure at the bottom of the test section is plotted over time. This represents the predicted measurement from the piezoelectric pressure sensor. As it is visible in Figure 3.2b, the chugging phenomenon is reproduced by the CHUG facility. Peaks of pressure up to 8.5 bar are simulated.

The shape of the pressure behaviour resembles exactly the one of chugging, as for example highlighted in [21, 36], where the shape of the chugging pressure waves is investigated. In particular, by looking at Figure 3.2c, where the liquid temperature at the injection point is plotted, it is possible to notice that the amplitude of pressure waves develops significantly when the temperature descends or ascends. The liquid temperature represents the temperature of the water boundary layer at the interface. With reference to Figure 1.9, the decrease in temperature represents the movement of the interface back in the injection tube while instead the increase in temperature highlights the movement of the interface towards the water of the test section. As in [36], it is thus found that the temperature of the water boundary layer at the interface becomes lower by mixing with the cool pool water around the interface while it ascends or descends. The presence of chugging is thus demonstrated.

The movement of the interface can be easily visualized by looking at the void fraction near the injection point. In Figure 3.2d the void fraction in the different radial rings of the injection level is represented. The interface moves fast and in significant extent as visible from the high-frequency changes of the void fraction. Moreover, the product between the interfacial area and the heat transfer coefficient (for both liquid and vapour) at the injection point is plotted in Figure 3.2e. This plot is characterized by several peaks that correspond to the moments when an enhanced mixing at the interface occurs, as predicted in [23]. By plotting the liquid mass flow rate at the injection point (Figure 3.2f), it is clearly visible that the peaks in the product between interfacial area and HTC correspond to the peaks in liquid velocity due to the ascension of the interface. However, it must be pointed out that the peaks are clearly exaggerated by numerical problems.

In order to study the dominant frequency of the chugging phenomenon, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is applied to the pressure data. FFT is an algorithm used to sample a signal over time in order to decompose it into its frequency components, that consist of sinusoidal oscillations characterized by frequency, amplitude and phase. In other words, the FFT is an algorithm able to apply the Fourier Transform to a discrete set of data.

Being N the data size and x_n a single datum, the definition of FFT is the following:

$$Y_k = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_n e^{-\frac{i2\pi kn}{N}} \quad \text{with } k = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (3.1)$$

The two-sided amplitude spectrum is then computed as:

$$P_2^k = \frac{Y_k}{N} \quad \text{with } k = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (3.2)$$

The two-sided spectrum includes the positive half of the frequencies followed by the negative half of the frequencies. The information about negative frequencies is redundant, since the spectrum of a real-world signal is symmetrical. Thus it is convenient to pass to a single-sided spectrum P_1 :

$$P_1 = \begin{cases} P_2^k & \text{for } k = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad k = \frac{N}{2} + 1 \\ 2 \times P_2^k & \text{for } 0 \leq k \leq \frac{N}{2} \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

Figure 3.2: Simulation parameters as computed by TRACE 2D model (base-case):

- (a) Steam mass flow rate at the injection pipe;
- (b) Pressure at the bottom of the test section;
- (c) Liquid temperature at the injection cell within the test section;
- (d) Void fraction at the injection level within the test section;
- (e) Product between HTC and interfacial area at the injection cell;
- (f) Liquid mass flow rate at the injection cell within the test section.

The single-sided amplitude spectrum of the pressure signal is depicted in Figure 3.3. It is visible how the most dominant frequency is around 5 Hz. However, a large spectrum of frequencies, from 2 to 8 Hz, results to be involved in the chugging phenomenon. Neither the low-frequency range (0-1 Hz) nor the high-frequency range (>10 Hz) are excited, contrarily to what expected from the linear stability analysis from [27].

Figure 3.3: Single-sided amplitude spectrum obtained from the FFT of the pressure signal at the bottom of the test section (TRACE 2D base-case).

It must be pointed out that the pressure oscillations involve also the injection (or vent) tube. In Figure 3.4 the pressure inside the injection tube is plotted. The magnitude of the pressure peaks present at the end of the injection tube is considerably greater than at the bottom of the test section. If these findings were true the integrity of the injection tube and of the steam generator would be threatened by these strong "chugs". In particular a huge pressure peak (up to 35 bar) is simulated at the end of the calculation, when the injection of steam stops and no counter-current flow is present at the injection tube. This leads the liquid re-entering the injection tube to hit the end wall and to produce a strong water-hammer. The presence of such strong pressure peaks are explainable by strong numerical instabilities within the resolution algorithm of TRACE.

The so-called water packing may indeed occur when the code tends to overfill ("pack") a cell already full of liquid or to overextract liquid from a liquid-full cell [33]. Water packing is strictly related to water hammers: when cold water flows down a dead-end pipe filled with steam, a sizeable pressure spike occurs at the moment when all the steam is collapsed, namely when the pipe is completely filled by water. It must be pointed out that this behaviour usually occurs in case of any Eulerian finite-difference scheme, where any boundary cell may behave as the dead-end of a pipe.

Water packing occurs mainly when condensation is present. The best way to explain water packing numerical instability is to look at an example [33]. Let us consider a 1D cell where sub-cooled liquid is flowing from the left and vapour is flowing from the right. As the vapour comes in contact with liquid it condenses and the cell is thus filled with liquid. For a standard finite-difference momentum equation it is impossible to produce a liquid mass flow out of the right face balancing the liquid mass flow in the left face at the moment when the cell is being filled by water, since the algorithm tends to predict a liquid mass flow entering from the right face due to the strong condensation event. In this case the code does not halt the flow as in case of water hammer, but forces the liquid to be pushed through the right face by increasing abruptly the pressure.

The presence of the water packing instability develops especially in 1D components such as VALVE

Figure 3.4: Pressure at the dead-end of the injection pipe (TRACE 2D base-case.)

and PIPE. In this simulation, the condensation of the vapour slug leads the upper and lower liquid fronts to collapse the steam in between and to collide causing a considerable pressure peak. This phenomenon is enhanced especially at the end of the simulation, when the injection of steam is stopped and the vapour in the injection tube is completely condensed by the re-entering water. That is why the huge pressure peaks occur at the end of the injection tube, modeled as 1D VALVE. Models for the mitigation of water packing are already present inside TRACE code. Their influence on the simulation results are assessed in a later sensitivity study.

In order to verify the correct prediction of the temperature distribution inside the test section, the temperatures at the three thermocouple positions are plotted in Figure 3.5a. In this case the results are presented for a simulation prolonged until 180 seconds (constant injection until 178 s with 1 s ramp-down to zero). In particular:

1. Thermocouple 1 (TC1): axial level 6 ($h = 0.25m$), radial ring 1 (25mm from the wall);
2. Thermocouple 2 (TC2): axial level 15 ($h = 0.70m$), radial ring 1 (25mm from the wall);
3. Thermocouple 3 (TC3): axial level 25 ($h = 1.20m$), radial ring 1 (25mm from the wall);

The temperature steadily rises until 120 seconds, when it seems to stabilize between 301 K and 302 K. If the heat loss through the inner surface of the heat structure (Figure 3.5c) is considered, this can be explained by the reaching of a sort of thermal equilibrium between the heat injected into the system in form of high-pressure steam and the heat exchange between the test section and the outer environment. The oscillations of the temperature can be explained by looking at the void fraction at the thermocouple positions over the simulation time (Figure 3.5b). The oscillations are caused by the appearance of the water-steam interface which causes an increase and a subsequent fast decrease in the temperature of the water boundary layer at the interface due to mixing with the cold pool water around the interface.

It must be noticed that no thermal stratification is predicted by TRACE code. The validity of this result is suspicious, since it was already stated in [30] that 1D TRACE simulations are not able to predict the thermal stratification in case of injection of steam in subcooled liquid. In this case, even if a low injection level correspondent to approximately a steam mass flux of $50 \frac{kg}{m^2 \times s}$ is employed, the TRACE 2D model does not seem to be able to simulate the thermal stratification envisaged in [29]. The capability of TRACE in predicting axial thermal stratification must be assessed against the experimental results.

Figure 3.5: Temperature (a), void fraction (b) at the three different thermocouple positions and heat loss (c) through the inner surface of the heat structure (TRACE 2D base-case).

3.4 Sensitivity Study

Starting from the base-case calculation presented in the previous section, a sensitivity study on several parameters of the simulation has been planned and performed.

First of all, it is important to evaluate the structure of the mesh. Thus, simulations were performed by using a finer or coarser mesh with respect to the base-case calculation in order to assess the influence of the modelling on the numerical results. The presence of the heat structure simulating the heat transfer between the test section and the surrounding environment has been as well investigated.

Then the influence of the injection mass flow rate has been assessed by performing TRACE simulations with different outputs from the steam generator. Moreover, the constant injection has been replaced with a sinusoidal type injection to reproduce the influence of the oscillatory void feedback effect in SFR reactor (cfr Chapter 1). This is similar to the simulation performed in [17] during the pre-conceptual design studies.

Finally, the water packing effect has been investigated by turning off the corresponding corrective option in TRACE solver.

3.4.1 1D case

In this case the 2D VESSEL component representing the test section is replaced by a 1D PIPE component. This sensitivity study is fundamental in the frame of reactor core simulations. In case of simulation of accidents like ULOF [7, 8], the core is usually represented by a multi-1D-channel model. In other words, each sub-assembly is modeled as 1D pipe with no influence on the other sub-assemblies other than the power and temperature distributions.

The 1D-model is thus suited for the assessment of the representability of the chugging phenomenon within a SFR core. It must be pointed out that in this case the injection of the steam does not stop at 59 seconds but it is kept constant until 60 seconds. The injection mass flow rate at the injection tube is presented in Figure 3.6a: it is clearly visible how the injection of steam inside the test section is either stopped or reversed due to the strong "chugs" occurring in the test section. Peaks of injection of steam up to 13 g/s due to numerical instability are simulated as well.

Figure 3.6: Simulation parameters as computed by TRACE 1D model: (a) Steam mass flow rate at the injection pipe; (b) Pressure at the bottom of the test section.

The strong chugs simulated in this case are visible in Figure 3.6b: pressure peaks reach a magnitude of more than 40 bar and are thus much stronger than the base-case. The considerable magnitude of the pressure peaks can be attributed to the phenomenon of the water packing, as described in previous section. The presence of a 1D component representing the test section leads to the enhancement of the water packing effect.

The result is the appearance of huge pressure peaks which are probably due to numerical errors. These data will be compared with the experimental results that will finally assess the validity of this type of simulations. It is important to mention that the presence of strong water packing must be addressed in the future for the simulations of two-phase accident scenarios like ULOF in multi-1D-channel model, since the prediction of the pressure waves generated in the process are fundamental to assure the integrity of the whole core structure.

The temperature distribution over time at the three thermocouple positions is depicted in Figure 3.7. When compared to the base-case (Figure 3.5a), it is possible to notice that the stratification of temperature is more emphasized in the 1D case. While the temperature measured by the three thermocouples is approximately the same in the 2D base-case, the 1D-model highlights a difference of temperature up to 10 K between TC1 and TC3 after 60 seconds. However, the thermal stratification predicted by the 1D model does not seem as enhanced as in previous studies like [29].

Finally, the void fraction 1D axial profile along the test section over time is plotted in Figure 3.8. The void profile can be compared to the one obtained during the ULOF transient in a SFR low-void

Figure 3.7: Temperature at the three different thermocouple positions (TRACE 1D case).

Figure 3.8: Evolution of the void axial profile along CHUG test section during vapour injection phase (TRACE 1D case).

core (Figure 1.6): in both cases the pressure peaks coincide with the moment when condensation of the vapour slug induces the two liquid fronts to bump into each other. The chugging phenomenon is then well reproduced by the CHUG 1D model, even if several numerical instabilities may overestimate the involved physical quantities.

Another important information in Figure 3.8 is the visualization of the water level trend. At certain instants the water level is predicted to even overcome the test section height, resulting in the spilling of water out of the facility. This problem has been taken into account in the design of the facility by building a shielding for the electronic equipment.

The behaviour of the vapour slug is also a very interesting outcome that must be further investigated. Figure 3.8 shows the formation of unique and compact slugs of vapour occupying all the section and collapsing as a whole. On the other hand, the 2D model generates slugs of vapour which do not cover the entire section, but only a limited number of radial rings. The consequence of this phenomenon is the contact between the slugs of vapour and the liquid present in the outer radial rings, which break the slugs in several part. Then, the minor slugs at an higher position collapse due to thermal effects, while the bubbles near the injection point are collapsed due to the movement and compression by the column of liquid standing above them. This may also explain the different of magnitude of the pressure peaks between the two cases.

The future steps of the CHUG project envisage the replacement of the steel section with an acrylic glass one that will render possible the visualization of the chugging phenomenon by an high-speed camera. It will be then possible to assess the real behaviour of the steam slug forming and collapsing inside the test section and causing the pressure peaks to develop.

3.4.2 Axial refinement

In this case the base 2D model has been refined axially by increasing the number of axial levels from 50 to 100, each with height equal to 25mm. The simulation stopped at 59 seconds due to numerical problems. However, the pressure at the bottom of the test section is plotted in Figure 3.9a. The influence of the axial refinement consists in damping the pressure peaks, which on average are 0.5 bar lower than in the base-case.

Figure 3.9: Simulation parameters as computed by TRACE axially refined 2D model: (a) Pressure at the bottom of the test section; (b) Temperature at the three different thermocouple positions.

The outcome from this simulation highlights the ability by the axial refinement of the 2D VESSEL component to damp the possible presence of water packing. It is however important to mention that it is usually advisable to set the height of the cells of hydraulic components at least as long as the hydraulic

diameter. The axial refinement shows an important property of the 2D component modelization but its validity must be assessed.

The evolution of the temperature at the thermocouple positions is depicted in Figure 3.9b. No substantial change is noticed by comparison to the base-case calculation. The axial temperature stratification tends to be better represented in case of a higher number of axial levels, as one may expect. However, the difference in temperature is not significant and may be due to the chaotic nature of the chugging phenomenon.

3.4.3 Radial refinement

In this case the base 2D model has been refined radially by increasing the number of axial levels from 3 to 5, each with approximately equal volume. The pressure at the bottom of the test section is plotted in Figure 3.10a. It is interesting to notice that the pressure peaks have lower magnitude even than in case of axial refinement (Figure 3.9a). The increase in the number of radial rings leads to a strong damping of the pressure waves deriving from the chugging phenomenon.

Figure 3.10: Simulation parameters as computed by TRACE radially refined 2D model: (a) Pressure at the bottom of the test section; (a) Void fraction at the 5 radial rings of the injection axial level; (c) Temperature at the three different thermocouple positions.

This may lead to the conclusion that a refined VESSEL 2D component tends to limit the development of water hammers. This can be visualized by plotting the void fraction in the 5 radial rings at the

injection point within the test section (Figure 3.10b). The vapor slug does not spread across the whole cross section of the pipe, but only from Ring 1 to Ring 3 in different extent. This causes the formation of a concentric water column surrounding the vapour slug and causing the condensation and break up of the latter. The chugging phenomenon is still occurring, as documented from the drops in void fraction due to the downward movement of the liquid column above caused by steam collapse. However, the thermal effects induced by the condensation process in the outer radial rings leads to damp the extent of the collapse by the liquid column movement. Moreover, since the liquid column is spread among several rings, the collapse of the vapour slug propagates along several directions. This means that the downward liquid mass flow is not able to collapse all the vapour at the injection point, as visible in Figure 3.10b, and that the radial refinement causes a strong damping of the pressure waves at the central ring of the test section.

The evolution of the temperature at the thermocouple positions is depicted in Figure 3.10c. No substantial change is noticed if compared to the base-case calculation.

3.4.4 Influence of the heat structure

In this case the base model has been modified by removing the heat structure. The simulation has been run for 180 seconds (constant injection stopped at 178 s with 1s ramp-down until zero). First of all, the thermocouples simulated measurement is presented in Figure 3.11. As expected, without heat loss through the test section surface the water temperature within the test section tends to linearly increase. In this case the temperature reaches 320 K after 180 seconds, significantly higher than in the base-case.

Figure 3.11: Temperature at the three different thermocouple positions (TRACE 2D case with no heat structure).

However, the most important outcome of this sensitivity study case is the disappearance of the chugging phenomenon at a certain instant of the simulation. By looking at the pressure at the bottom of the test section (Figure 3.12a) it is visible how the pressure oscillations characteristic of chugging cease after approximately 170 seconds. If the void fraction at different levels above the injection point is plotted (Figure 3.12b), it is noticeable how the steam bubbles injected inside the test section rapidly and continuously condense without causing oscillations in pressure.

The explanation for this fast disappearance of the chugging phenomenon can be found by looking at the condensation regime map from [23] (Figure 1.13), where the conditions for the occurrence of steam

Figure 3.12: Simulation parameters as computed by TRACE 2D model with no heat structure: (a) Pressure at the bottom of the test section; (b) Void fraction in central ring of 4 different axial levels (cell height = 5 cm).

chugging for upward injection are shown to have an upper limit for both liquid temperature and steam injection mass flow rate. Since the water temperature in the CHUG test section increases permanently, when it overcomes the threshold for the chugging physical conditions at fixed injection mass flow rate the chugging phenomenon disappears being substituted with the bubbling regime.

The outcome from this case study highlights the importance of setting the experimental parameters in order to reproduce correctly the conditions for the chugging phenomenon. The base-case parameters seem however within the physical conditions for the chugging phenomenon to occur.

3.4.5 Mass Flow rate

In this case the influence of the injection mass flow rate of steam is assessed by comparing simulations performed with 4 different injection mass flow rates ($m_{inj} = 0.75, 1, 1.5, 2$ g/s). The injection is kept constant until the end of the simulation, without ramp-down.

The pressure at the bottom of the test section measured in the 4 different cases is highlighted in Figure 3.13, along with the corresponding FFT. The FFT curve tends to be lowered as the injection mass flow rate increases. This is caused by the reduction of the pressure peaks due to the chugging phenomenon as the mass flow rate increases.

In particular, by looking at the $m_{inj} = 1.5$ g/s case, it can be noticed that for about 15 seconds of the simulated time the pressure oscillation are considerably lower in magnitude with respect to the other cases. This may be explained by pointing out the difference between chugging and condensation oscillations. As explained in [21], chugging and condensation oscillations have the same nature: the pressure oscillations are caused by the increased mixing at the interface and the movement of the latter. However, chugging causes the oscillations of pressure to be more violent and occurs when the interface streams upwards and downwards the injection tube. On the contrary, condensation oscillations are weaker and happen when the movement of the interface occurs outside the injection tube, within the water pool. By increasing the steam injection mass flow rate, the interface tends to remain far from the injection tube and the oscillations are weaker, as demonstrated in the $m_{inj} = 1.5$ g/s case. However, the relative amplitude spectrum does not show the excitation of the high frequency components related to condensation oscillations and interface movement. Thus, condensation oscillations are not captured by TRACE, probably because the steam-water interface is not resolved by the code.

A more accurate explanation is related to the enhancement of the counter current flow at the steam injection point due to the increase of the vapour mass flow rate. This effect hinders the collapse of the

(a) $m_{inj} = 0.75g/s$ - Pressure

(b) $m_{inj} = 0.75g/s$ - FFT

(c) $m_{inj} = 1.0g/s$ - Pressure

(d) $m_{inj} = 1.0g/s$ - FFT

(e) $m_{inj} = 1.5g/s$ - Pressure

(f) $m_{inj} = 1.5g/s$ - FFT

(g) $m_{inj} = 2.0g/s$ - Pressure

(h) $m_{inj} = 2.0g/s$ - FFT

Figure 3.13: Sensitivity study on steam injection mass flow rate (TRACE 2D model) effect on pressure at the bottom of the test section and FFT of the pressure signal.

vapour slug near the injection point and leads to the damping of the pressure oscillations. However, since the chugging phenomenon is significantly chaotic, it is not clear from this sensitivity study the reason why the damping of pressure oscillations occurs only in restricted intervals. For instance, the $m_{inj} = 2$ g/s case shows that there is no clear correlation between injection mass flow rate and extent and occurrence of pressure oscillations. This thermal-hydraulic instability only reveals to be extremely chaotic and its outcome to be extremely stochastic.

3.4.6 Sinusoidal Injection

As already performed in the previous study from the author [17], a sinusoidal steam injection is simulated in order to reproduce the behavior of sodium boiling inside SFR assembly in case of ULOF transient. In this case the chugging phenomenon is coupled with the neutronic reactivity feedbacks characterizing the low-void core design: when the vapour is generated at the top of the fuel sub-assembly, the negative void feedback leads to the power decrease and to the drastic reduction of the amount of steam generated. On the other hand, when the vapour collapses, the power rises up again due to the positive reactivity insertion. The behaviour inside the assembly can be thus reproduced by a sinusoidal injection. As in [17], the period of the sinus is chosen to be equal to 4 seconds. The mass flow rate at the injection tube is plotted in Figure 3.14.

Figure 3.14: Steam mass flow rate at the injection pipe (TRACE 2D case with sinusoidal injection).

In Figure 3.15 the pressure at the bottom of the test section along with the corresponding FFT is presented. It can be noticed how the strongest peaks of pressure occur in correspondence of the minimum injection, namely at the instants when the injection is equal or very close to zero. As visible from the liquid mass flow rate at the injection point (Figure 3.16), no counter-current flow occurs and the water falls downwards where either bumps into the stagnant liquid front or re-enters inside the injection tube.

The most important feature to point out is that the amplitude spectrum of Figure 3.15b does not look altered by the presence of the sinusoidal injection pattern. The same frequencies characteristic of chugging are excited and there is no major change caused by the forced sinusoidal behavior of the simulation test. This highlights that the chugging phenomenon tends to occur even without the presence of strong void feedback making the vapour generation to oscillate. The occurrence chugging thermal-hydraulic instability occurring in SFR reactors may be considered to be independent from neutronic parameters, as already stated in [8].

Figure 3.15: (a) Pressure at the bottom of the test section and b corresponding FFT (TRACE 2D case with sinusoidal injection).

Figure 3.16: Liquid mass flow rate at the injection cell within the test section (TRACE 2D case with sinusoidal injection).

3.4.7 Water packing

As already mentioned above, water packing numerical instability may affect the results of the simulation in case of strong condensation as in CHUG experiment. TRACE adopts a method for mitigating water-packing that is similar in spirit to shock-fitting techniques [33].

Pressure excursions caused by water-packing are detected by a built-in logic. Thus, when the finite-difference momentum equation is producing invalid results due to water packing, the momentum equation at those locations and times are modified with the purpose of obtaining a more suited solution. The standard motion equation at a cell edge can be written as:

$$v_{j+1/2}^{n+1} = v_{j+1/2}^n + a + b(P_j^{n+1} - P_{j+1}^{n+1}) \quad (3.4)$$

where v and P velocity and pressure, respectively, the subscript denotes the number of cell edge and the superscript the number of time step. a incorporates additional force terms and b includes the time-step size and inverse of mesh length and density.

Figure 3.17: (a) Pressure at the bottom of the test section and b at the dead-end of the injection tube (TRACE 2D case with no water packing mitigation).

If water packing is detected in cell j , the equation is modified to:

$$v_{j+1/2}^{n+1} = v_{j+1/2}^n + a + b(cP_j^{n+1} - P_{j+1}^{n+1}) \quad (3.5)$$

by taking c as a relatively large number in order to limit the increase in pressure needed to push the liquid through the next edge. Moreover, the value of b in the vapour equation is set equal to the corresponding coefficient in the liquid equation to avoid exaggerated vapour velocities.

It is important to mention that the logic of water packing is triggered only in case of numerical instability and not in case of a true water-hammer-type phenomenon.

In order to assess the influence of the mentioned model on the results and to actually verify if the model intervenes in the calculation, the water packing correction has been deactivated in this sensitivity study.

Two cases are taken into consideration: the base-case 2D calculation and the 1D calculation where the test section is modeled as a PIPE component.

In the first case, as visible in Figure 3.17a, the magnitude of the pressure peaks at the bottom of the test section is slightly increased. This has the profound meaning that the water packing effect intervenes in the simulations conducted until here and has to be taken care of in the evaluation of results.

However, in Figure 3.17b, where the pressure at the injection tube is plotted, it is visible how the pressure peaks are not different from the case where the mitigating model is present. This highlights how this peak of pressure is probably due to a water hammer. Therefore, the mitigating model does not intervene and no mitigation occurs. Even if the mitigation model does not play a significant role, it is important to point out that it may be possible that the peaks of pressure in the base-case calculation are still affected by a level of numerical error. The experimental tests must address also this issue.

As a proof of what has been just explained, in case of employment of the 1D model (Figure 3.18) the peaks are even more exaggerated, reaching up to 120 bar. The utilization of 1D components for the simulation of this type of thermal-hydraulic instability may lead to overestimation of the pressure effects on the system. This has to be seriously taken into account for the simulation of SFR core behaviour.

Figure 3.18: Pressure at the bottom of the test section (TRACE 1D case with no water packing mitigation).

Chapter 4

PSI-BOIL pre-calculations

This chapter presents calculations performed with the state-of-the-art in-house PSI's DNS tool for simulation of multiphase flow, called PSI-BOIL (Parallel Simulator of BOILing). The aim of these calculations is the investigation of the behaviour of high-pressure steam bubbles injected in cold water, in analogy to the performed CHUG experimental tests.

The collapse of bubbles in a cold pool is fundamental in order to understand the phenomenology of the ULOF transient in SFR low-void core designs. As already explained in Section 1.3.4, the vapour slug developing at the upper region of SFR sub-assemblies starts collapsing when it comes in contact with the colder liquid sodium present in the upper plenum. This phenomenon can be mocked up as the injection of sodium vapour into the sub-cooled liquid sodium of the upper plenum. The understanding of the mechanism of collapse of bubbles becomes thus fundamental for an accurate description of the chugging phenomenon developing in SFR sub-assemblies during the ULOF transient.

For this purpose, future studies are planned for the implementation of sodium properties into PSI-BOIL in order to reproduce sodium boiling. But before starting any attempt to simulate the behaviour of a liquid metal, it is important to evaluate the case with water, which has proven to play the role of sodium simulant. In this study, several simulations were performed by implementing some sodium properties in order to evaluate the influence of the difference of surface tension and thermal conductivity between water and sodium on the collapse of the bubbles.

Therefore, an assessment on the correctness of using water as a sodium simulant is performed, as well as a first evaluation of the problems related to the simulation of liquid metal behaviour with PSI-BOIL.

However, the main aim of PSI-BOIL pre-calculations are related to the CHUG experimental tests. All the boundary conditions of the simulations performed by PSI-BOIL are set by considering water and steam properties predicted in the CHUG experiment. As already mentioned in Section 1.6, the second phase of the CHUG project envisages the substitution of the upper part of the steel test section with a corresponding one made of acrylic glass, which will enable the visualisation of the vapour bubbles behaviour through the use of a high-speed camera. It will be then possible to compare the results obtained from PSI-BOIL pre-calculations with the actual experimental behaviour. This will allow assessing the validity of bubble collapse simulations, which are always surrounded by an air of uncertainty.

In the following section, the PSI-BOIL code will be shortly presented and described. Then, a literature overview on the bubble collapse in subcooled liquid will be highlighted, followed by the results of the simulations performed by employing water properties. Finally, a sensitivity study on surface tension and thermal conductivity is presented by implementing some of the sodium properties into the previous calculations performed with water.

4.1 PSI-BOIL

The development of PSI-BOIL started in 2006 at Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI) in the framework of Multi-Scale Modelling Analysis (MSMA) project, whose main purpose is to formulate improved closure laws for Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations for prediction of convecting boiling and Critical Heat Flux (CHF) through the application of a multi-scale approach [37]. PSI-BOIL is a highly efficient, parallel DNS solver able to simulate boiling phenomena down to the meso-scale (millimetres), namely the scale of bubbles growing and detaching from the wall where thermal and velocity boundary layers adjacent to the bubbles are fully resolved.

PSI-BOIL does not aim to compete with commercial Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) codes but rather to serve as a numerical model development tool for the academic community. That is why PSI-BOIL is not an integral program capable of solving a general fluid flow problem but it is rather a suite of objects and algorithms used as blocks in order to build targeted programs for particular flow problems.

More precisely, PSI-BOIL (Parallel SIMulator of BOILing phenomena) is a three-dimensional, numerical solver for single- and two-phase flows with or without heat transfer. The discretisation of the governing equations is based on the second order accurate Finite Volume (FV) method on staggered orthogonal grids. The fractional step method [38] (also called projection method) is used for the coupling of the velocity and pressure fields, while a single set of incompressible Navier-Stokes equations is solved. The Navier-Stokes solver is coupled with an enthalpy conservation equation solver and a sharp-interface change model. Linear solvers are based on the Krylov's sub-space family of algorithms, which can be accelerated with an algebraic multigrid method.

The interface behaviour in two-phase flows is simulated through the surface tracking algorithm, based on the conservative, two-phase model proposed in [39]. In particular, the CIP-CSL2 method (Constrained Interpolated Profile method: Conservative Semi-Lagrangian 2nd order scheme) [40], which is able to maintain strict mass conservation, is employed along with an interface sharpening model to prevent smearing of the color function.

The mass transfer rate through the interface, positive for evaporation and negative for condensation, is calculated directly from the heat flux at the interface through the sharp-interface change model proposed in [41]. In this model, the phase change is assumed to occur only at the so-called "interface cells", which represent the computational cells containing part of the interface. The distribution of the mass transfer is kept sharp allowing the capture of the velocity jump across the interface.

The algorithm for the resolution of the system of equations [41] is the following:

1. Calculation of the mass transfer rate through the sharp-interface phase-change model;
2. Calculation of the body force including surface tension and gravity forces;
3. Update of the velocity and pressure fields through the projection method;
4. Update of the color function through the interface tracking method;
5. Update of the temperature through the energy balance equation solver;
6. Advancement of the time step and return to step 1. The time increment at each time step is given by:

$$\Delta t = \min \left(c_{CFL} \frac{\Delta x}{|\vec{u}|_{max}}, \left(\frac{\rho_v \Delta x^3}{2\pi\sigma} \right)^{0.5} \right) \quad (4.1)$$

where c_{CFL} is a dimensionless constant representing a safety factor.

A detailed description of the various applied methods and equations can be found in [41].

4.2 Bubble collapse in sub-cooled liquid

The research on the behaviour of a bubble collapsing in a subcooled liquid has been developed in great extent, especially because of the noise and material damage (e.g. erosion) that can be caused by the high velocities, pressures and temperatures that may result from that collapse [42]. The behaviour of bubble collapse is also important for the understanding of instability conditions in two-phase flow with subcooled boiling and in cavitation bubble dynamics.

A multitude of experiments and theoretical studies have been performed to assess closure relationship between the physical quantities governing the bubble behaviour and to study and visualize the bubble shape and the creation of water jets during bubble collapse. Below, a brief summary of the most relevant experimental and theoretical results is presented.

The collapse behaviour of a steam bubble undergoing condensation in subcooled liquid can be controlled by two different mechanisms [43, 44]:

1. the heat transfer processes occurring at the vapour-liquid phase interface;
2. the inertia of the liquid mass entering in form of jets into the space left free by the condensing vapour.

The heat transfer processes at the phase interface are influenced by the thermo-physical properties like heat conductivity, specific heat, latent heat of evaporation, density, viscosity and surface tension. That is why empirical correlations usually rely on the use of the Prandtl, Reynolds and Peclet numbers. A list of empirical correlations regarding the collapse of bubbles in subcooled liquid can be found in [44]. The most important non-dimensional parameter involved in the collapse of bubbles and determining whether the heat-transfer or the inertia driven bubble behaviour is the *Jakob number*, defined as:

$$Ja = \frac{\rho_l c_{p,l} (T_{sat} - T_l)}{H_{latent}} \quad (4.2)$$

where ρ_l , $c_{p,l}$ and T_l are the density, isobaric specific heat capacity and temperature of liquid, respectively; T_{sat} is the saturation temperature; H_{latent} is the latent heat of evaporation.

The Jakob number represents the ratio of sensible heat to latent heat released by the bubble during the condensation process. This quantity reveals to be very important, since it highlights which is the driving factor for the collapse of bubbles in subcooled liquid. As shown in [43], from experimental analysis the heat transfer driven and inertia driven condensation can be easily distinguished by measuring the pressure fluctuations around the bubble during condensation. In Figure 4.1 [43] it is possible to notice how the maximum amplitude of pressure fluctuations as a function of Jakob number in logarithmic scale show a linear relationship. More importantly, the slope of the linear trend changes significantly at $Ja = 100$. From this we can deduce that for $Ja < 100$ the bubble collapse is driven by heat transfer processes while for $Ja > 100$ the bubble collapse is subject to stronger pressure oscillations and is driven by inertia effects.

Therefore, the degree of subcooling of the liquid is the decisive factor concerning the mode of collapse. When the subcooling of water is relatively small heat transfer driven processes are dominant. As described in [45], for bubble collapse from an equilibrium state in a liquid of small superheat the temperature at the bubble surface quickly approaches to the saturation value corresponding to the external pressure and hence the pressure difference becomes essentially zero. The liquid inertia may thus be neglected and the collapse is controlled by the rate of heat transfer from the bubble surface to the liquid.

It is very interesting to visualize the behaviour of the thermal boundary layer. In [44] interferograms of a condensing bubble were utilised for different Ja values. In Figure 4.2 the interferogram for a thermally driven collapse ($Ja = 7.1$) of a propanol bubble is depicted. The boundary layer behaviour changes considerably from bubble formation to bubble detachment. However, it is visible how the behaviour is quite different for the bubble top and the bubble root. A stable laminar boundary layer develops around the bubble during formation process. On the other hand, it becomes significantly thinner at the top of

Figure 4.1: Maximum pressure fluctuations at the end of bubble collapse phase as a function of the Jakob number from [43].

Figure 4.2: Interferogram of a condensing propanol bubble ($p = 2$ bar, $\Delta T = 7.6$ K, $Ja = 7.1$) from [44].

the bubble at the instant when detachment starts, while around the lower surface some small oscillations produce high turbulent vortices in the drift flow.

Regarding the reduction of volume as a function of time, [45] proposes two models for the heat transfer driven collapse. The first one is based on the plane-interface approximation, where the effects of surface curvature and convective heat transport are neglected. The second model, more accurate and developed by Plesset and Zwick [46], is called zero-order temperature approximation and based on the assumption that appreciable temperature variations occur only in a thin layer adjacent to the boundary. The results are shown in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Evolution of radius over time for heat transfer driven collapse from [45].

In case of high subcooling ($Ja > 100$) heat transfer effects are negligible and the vapour pressure remains close to its initial value. In this case liquid inertia plays the dominant role, meaning that the behaviour of the bubble resembles the one of cavitation bubbles.

Cavitation bubble behaviour was first described by Lord Rayleigh [47], who distinguished two main stages of the motion of the radius during spherical bubble collapse with no heat transfer influence:

1. An asymptotic collapse stage where $\dot{R} \propto R^{-\frac{3}{2}}$, occurring before the significant compression of the gaseous content;
2. A rebound stage, where the acceleration \ddot{R} reverses sign and assumes a very large positive value.

It must be pointed out that the stability characteristics of the two stages are very different [42]. On one hand, the bubble in the first stage is overall stable, with disturbances on the bubble surface developing only slowly. On the other hand, due to the large \ddot{R} , the second phase is characterized by a great instability manifesting in significant spherical disturbances. The instability behaviour is highly dependent on the violence of the collapse and the presence of other boundaries. All bubbles collapsing to a size orders of magnitude smaller than their initial size are more keen to be broken up in a cloud of smaller bubbles. This fragmentation could be caused by a single microjet of water or it could be due to a spherical harmonic disturbance of higher order.

The most common occurrence is the development of a reentrant jet due to an asymmetry such as the presence of a pressure gradient or a nearby solid boundary. This phenomenology is well explained in [48], where the behaviour of collapsing cavities in presence of large departures from spherical symmetry is highlighted. A simple system where a deformable body is placed in motion by an impulse through a fluid is considered. By the use of the conservation of the Kelvin impulse, it is explained that a jet forms by involution at the back of the cavity and a hollow vortex ring appears, making the cavity assume the form of a torus. In order for the Kelvin impulse to be conserved in the system, the cavity would have to reach an infinite velocity of translation, which is impossible since the pressure over its surface is rather uniform. The fluid ends up possessing the Kelvin impulse in form of a vortex system which penetrates the bubble and in most cases causes collapse.

Thus, an asymmetry triggered by an impulse causes one side of the bubble to accelerate inward more rapidly than the opposite side and this results in the development of a high-speed re-entrant microjet which penetrates the bubble. Such an asymmetry can be even caused by the presence of a solid boundary, which produces a microjet against the boundary: this situation is the main responsible for damages to pipes and pumps when cavitation occurs [42].

However, the impulse causing the liquid microjet to develop can be attributed even to a gradient of pressure such as the hydrostatic one. In other words, in presence of gravity an upward jet progresses through the bubble and penetrates into the fluid on the other side, creating a conical protrusion on the upper part of the bubble surface. An example of this type of gravity-induced bubble behaviour is taken from [48] and depicted in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Image of the effect of a gravity-induced upward jet on a collapsing bubble from [48].

The creation of an upward reentrant microjet can occur also at the moment of bubble detachment in case of vapour injected through an orifice. As shown in [49] (Figure 4.5), a high-velocity microjet is generated in the wake at the bottom of the bubble at the moment of detachment and penetrates the bubble upwards, similarly to cavitation phenomena. The microjet formation is attributed to the impulse given by the surface tension "rebound" occurring at the moment of bubble detachment, as well as to the large depression developing in the wake of the bubble, which causes the liquid to be accelerated towards the bubble. Another interesting phenomenon observed in [49] is the formation of a secondary vapour bubble below the primary which is pushed upwards and coalesces with the primary bubble before the collapse caused by the liquid microjet. This is attributable to the formation of a hot spot beneath the centre of the primary bubble during adherence to the orifice outlet.

An alternative way to bubble break-up is the development of harmonic disturbances on the surface of the bubble. This phenomenon is highlighted in the experimental study from [50], where bubbles injected in a subcooled pool undergo harmonic disturbances on the top of the bubble leading to the so-called Microbubble Emission Boiling (MEB) phenomenon.

As depicted in Figure 4.6, while the bubble interface is smooth at the early stage of condensation, a harmonic disturbance occurs at the top region of the bubble. The interface instability is driven by the condensation process, which causes a significant depression inside the bubble. Such a sudden drop of pressure inside the vapor bubble and inertia effects lead to the development of a fine Rayleigh-Taylor-like instability over the free surface, which increases the heat transfer area and thus enhances the condensa-

Figure 4.5: Bubble collapse history for steam injected through an orifice from [49]. $P = 4\text{bar}$, $\Delta T_{\text{subcooling}} = 30\text{K}$, 2.5 frames per second.

Figure 4.6: Successive images of the condensing/collapsing vapor bubble through the orifice, highlighting microbubble emission ($\Delta T_{\text{subcooling}} = 32\text{K}$) [50].

tion process. Finally, the fine disturbances on the surface cause the break-up of the primary bubble into a multitude of microbubbles, realising the MEB.

Regarding the thermal boundary layer behaviour for inertia-driven collapse, in [44] the interferogram of a condensing ethanol bubble at high Ja is presented (Figure 4.7). The situation is completely different from the one in Figure 4.2: due to the instability of the interface caused by local condensation effects, no stable laminar boundary layer develops around the bubble and the complete condensation occurs in very short time.

Figure 4.7: Interferogram of a condensing ethanol bubble at high Ja ($p = 0.25$ bar, $\Delta T = 20.6$ K, $Ja = 101.2$) from [44].

The reduction of volume as a function of time for inertia driven collapse, proposed by [45] and depicted in Figure 4.8 for a spherical bubble, follows the Rayleigh solution [47] and reveals to be much more abrupt than in case of heat transfer driven collapse (Figure 4.8).

Apart from what mentioned above, there are other multiple effects influencing the behaviour of bubbles condensing in subcooled pool. For example, in [51] the influence of the non-linear effect resulting from finite wavelength of sound waves in liquid, called Bjerknes Force, is investigated theoretically for bubbles in an acoustic field. However, it is shown that when buoyancy force prevails the bubble behaviour resembles the collapse under gravity shown by [48].

Finally, it is important to mention that the collapse of the bubble due to liquid inertia brings about the propagation of pressure shock waves at the moment of the rebound stage. In [52] it is demonstrated that the impulsive pressure impinging on the wall is due to the propagation of this shock wave and that no major effect is caused by the impingement of the liquid jet to the boundary. The pressure waves generated by the collapse of a condensing bubble can reach up to $10^5 atm$ with a duration of around $2 - 3 \mu s$. Thus, it is important to account for this behaviour in the study of the behaviour in case of bubble collapse inside the upper plenum of SFR, since it can endanger the surrounding structures.

Figure 4.8: Evolution of radius over time for inertia driven collapse from [45].

4.3 PSI-BOIL simulation of condensing bubble collapse under CHUG conditions

In this study the DNS code PSI-BOIL has been employed for the simulation of condensing bubble collapse under the conditions of the CHUG experiment. Thus, high-pressure steam ($T = 151.8^\circ\text{C}$, $p = 5\text{bar}$) is injected into a column of subcooled water ($T = 20^\circ\text{C}$, $p = 1\text{bar}$) through an orifice and the collapsing behaviour is investigated. This situation corresponds to a Jakob number equal to 148, thus a collapse driven by liquid inertia is expected to occur.

The computational domain is represented in the scheme of Figure 4.9. Its dimensions are $2\text{cm} \times 2\text{cm} \times 8\text{cm}$ in both lateral directions and vertical direction, respectively, using $64 \times 64 \times 256$ cells. It must be pointed out that the grid is kept coarse in order to speed up the computation time and to assess the capability of PSI-BOIL to capture condensing phenomena even without the use of a very fine grid. The steam is injected upwards through a square of $3.75\text{mm} \times 3.75\text{mm}$ (12×12 cells) situated at the bottom face of the domain with a vertical velocity equal to $1 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$.

The boundary conditions employed for steam and water in this calculation are listed in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Water and steam boundary conditions for the simulation of condensing bubble collapse under CHUG conditions performed by PSI-BOIL.

Property	Water	Steam
Pressure	1 bar	5 bar
Temperature	20°C	151.8°C
Viscosity	0.001 Pa·s	1.396×10^{-5} Pa·s
Density	$1000 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$	$2.668 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$
Specific Heat Capacity (C_p)	$4184 \frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}\cdot\text{K}}$	$2410 \frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}\cdot\text{K}}$
Thermal Conductivity	$0.600 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}}$	$0.03025 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}}$
Saturation Temperature		100°C
Surface Tension		$0.059 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}}$
Latent Heat		$2.258 \times 10^6 \frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}}$

Before presenting the results, it is essential to understand the capabilities of PSI-BOIL regarding the simulation of bubble collapse. Since PSI-BOIL employs the assumption of incompressible fluid, all the phenomena involving compressibility properties cannot be simulated. This means that in the Rayleigh solution for inertia driven collapse the rebound stage, which includes water compressibility, cannot be reproduced. The same can be said of the Bjerknes force and the propagation of shock waves through the

Figure 4.9: Scheme of the computational domain used for PSI-BOIL pre-calculations.

water pool.

However, it is important to verify if PSI-BOIL is able to reproduce the deformation of the bubble due to the liquid microjets as the one generated in a gravity field or after the detachment of the bubble. In this analysis the pressure evolution is not taken into account, since it would be impossible to recognize the pressure waves generated by the bubble collapse.

Moreover, the coarse grid renders impossible both the resolution of the thermal boundary layer and the reproduction of the fine disturbances generating on the bubble surface in case of microbubble emission. For this purpose, a future analysis with a much finer grid is envisaged to study the influence of grid refinement and investigate more detailed phenomena.

The computed evolution of bubble is shown in Figure 4.11 for the first bubble and Figure 4.14 for the second bubble. It is indeed important to investigate the influence of the hot wake left by the first bubble condensation on the collapse of the subsequent bubbles.

In Figure 4.11 it is visible how the bubble behaviour resembles well the experimental result shown by [49] (Figure 4.5) regarding the collapse of a bubble after detachment from an orifice. The bubble surface at the top shows an upward protrusion while on the bottom of the bubble the interface shows an inward recess. This asymmetry is the cause of the development of a liquid microjet which penetrates the bubble and causes the bubble to break up into smaller bubbles. The development of the liquid microjet can be mainly attributed to the "rebound" caused by the surface tension at the moment of detachment and to the condensation effects at the root of the bubble. Enhanced condensation due to the high Ja value creates a depression where the liquid is accelerated and penetrates the bubble.

Another important aspect to take into account is the effect of gravity. As soon as the bubble detaches

Figure 4.10: (a) Volume and (b) equivalent radius evolution over time for the first condensing steam bubble in subcooled water under CHUG experimental conditions simulated by PSI-BOIL. $t = 0$ is equivalent to t_0 in Figure 4.11.

from the steam column at the orifice, it undergoes an impulse due to the hydrostatic pressure gradient, as explained by [48]. Thus, the liquid microjet is caused by the concurrence of both condensation and gravity effects.

Another observable phenomenon is the formation of secondary vapour bubbles in the wake of the primary bubble, as already shown experimentally by [49]. These bubbles are accelerated towards the primary bubble and eventually coalesce with the primary bubble or condense in the colder water pool.

The volume of the bubble and its equivalent radius are plotted over time in Figure 4.10. The measurement of the volume of the bubble in the grid has been made possible thanks to a new "Floodfill" algorithm developed at PSI and that will be subject to publication.

If the plots of Figure 4.10 are compared to the predictions of [45] (Figures 4.3, 4.8), it is possible to see how the collapse of the simulated bubble can be divided in two phases. In the first phase until bubble break-up, the liquid inertia driven collapse is representative of the behaviour of the bubble, even if mitigated by the thermal effects which render the collapse slower. A considerable drop of volume occurs at the moment of break-up highlighting the strong influence of liquid inertia on the mode of collapse. On the other hand, in the second phase, when smaller bubbles appear, the collapse behaviour resembles more the thermal driven one. This may be due to the coarseness of the grid that does not allow the development of water microjets breaking up such small bubbles. Also, the compressibility, playing a major role in the inertia driven collapse of water, cannot be represented by PSI-BOIL. However, given that the prediction from [45] envisages a spherical bubble, the prediction of the volume of the bubble by PSI-BOIL over time is satisfactory from an overall point of view.

In Figure 4.12 the temperature and velocity fields are depicted at six different instants of the first bubble collapse on the central plane perpendicular to the y -coordinate. As already mentioned above, the coarse grid employed in the simulation does not allow the resolution of the thermal boundary layer around the bubble. In PSI-BOIL the phase interface is modelled to be always at the saturation temperature, which in case of the cold water pool is equal to 100°C . However, the temperature field around the root of the bubble shows a very unstable behaviour. A numerical instability causes the temperature around the secondary bubble column to reach values higher than the saturation temperature and thus to cause evaporation at the root of the primary bubble before detachment. It is also important to observe the hot wake left by the primary bubble behind its upward path.

By looking at the velocity field it is interesting to notice how before bubble detachment some swirling current develops inside the bubble near the interface. This is similar to the eddy currents numerically provoked by the surface tension term in the Navier-Stokes equation. More interestingly, it is important to observe the formation of large upward velocities at the central

vertical line of the bubble which cause the formation of the upward protrusion. This velocity field develops at the moment of the inward bending at the root of the vapour column. The explanation of this phenomenon can be referred to the necking phenomenon described in [24]. The unstable interface of the steam pocket tends to shrink the "bottle-neck" connecting the steam pocket to the source of vapour. The decrease of the bottle-neck cross section leads to an increase of the vapour flow through it causing the appearance of a strong velocity field inside the forming bubble. Alongside with this phenomenon, the enhanced condensation process in the root of the bubble causes the vapour column to bend inwards and accelerates the liquid towards the interface. As a result, the bubble detaches with an inward recess and a liquid jet penetrates the bubble and causes it to break up in several smaller bubbles.

In Figure 4.13 the mass transfer rate at the phase interface is depicted along with the isothermal lines corresponding to the saturation temperature on the central plane perpendicular to the y -coordinate. It is clearly visible how the fast condensation leads to the evaporation at the inward recess of the vapour column, highlighting the presence of an unstable thermal boundary layer. However, it is visible how the condensation rate is significantly high at the surface of the bubble throughout all the process. Moreover, as soon as the bubble detaches from the orifice a strong condensation phenomenon leads to the collapse in short instants of time.

In Figure 4.14 the evolution of the second bubble detaching from the orifice is depicted. It is visible how the collapse of this bubble is significantly slower than the one of the previous bubble. This is explainable by the presence of the hot wake left by the first bubble that shapes the disturbances at the upper surface of the second bubble.

In Figure 4.15 the temperature and velocity fields of the second bubble are plotted over time on the central plane perpendicular to the y -coordinate. The disturbance on the surface of the bubble is limited to one major upward protrusion at the top of the bubble, due to the hot water heated up by the passage of the previous bubble. However, it is clearly visible how a liquid jet develops and penetrates the bubble similarly to the previous case, leading to its break-up. The magnitude of the velocity field developing is considerably smaller than in the case of the first bubble, showing how an highest degree of subcooling leads to the development of stronger effects. The shape of the bubble at the later stages of collapse is very similar to the experimental findings of [49], especially because the hot wake of the first bubble causes the degree of subcooling to be closer to the cited experimental conditions.

The overall conclusion related to the results of the simulation of CHUG conditions is that the behaviour of a bubble collapsing in a subcooled water pool is qualitatively reproduced by PSI-BOIL in a satisfactory way consistent to the experimental results cited in the previous chapter. The formation of an upward liquid jet is well highlighted in the results as well as the disturbances generated due to the enhanced condensation process and gravity effects.

However, the coarseness of the grid does not allow a deep investigation on the thermal boundary layer at the bubble surface, which anyway does not have a stable behaviour due to numerical instabilities caused by the fast condensation process.

The liquid inertia driven collapse is only partly reproduced and the influence of heat transfer effects is not negligible. The lack of the compressibility properties of the fluid does not allow capturing all the phenomena related to the collapse of bubbles at high Ja values. However, it will be very interesting to compare the results obtained by PSI-BOIL with the actual behaviour occurring in CHUG experimental tests when the steel test section will be replaced by an acrylic glass one and the use of an high speed camera will allow the visualization of the collapse of bubbles inside the facility.

Figure 4.11: Collapse of the first condensing steam bubble in subcooled water under CHUG experimental conditions simulated by PSI-BOIL.

Figure 4.12: Temperature and velocity fields during the collapse of the first condensing steam bubble in subcooled water under CHUG experimental conditions simulated by PSI-BOIL.

Figure 4.13: Mass heat transfer rate at the interface during the collapse of the first condensing steam bubble in subcooled water under CHUG experimental conditions simulated by PSI-BOIL. The saturation temperature isoline is highlighted in violet.

Figure 4.14: Collapse of the second condensing steam bubble in subcooled water under CHUG experimental conditions simulated by PSI-BOIL.

Figure 4.15: Temperature and velocity fields during the collapse of the second condensing steam bubble in subcooled water under CHUG experimental conditions simulated by PSI-BOIL.

4.4 Sensitivity study on Sodium properties

In this chapter a sensitivity study on various sodium properties is proposed. Since PSI-BOIL was essentially developed for the phase change of water, the simulation of sodium condensation cannot be done by simply replacing the material properties of water to the ones of sodium. Sodium condensation simulations result indeed in too high velocity caused by the high intensity of condensation. However, future projects at PSI envisage the implementation of sodium properties in order to cope with the behaviour of sodium boiling, fundamental for the description of the transients occurring in SFRs. In this study, the input file of the simulation employing water under CHUG experimental conditions has been modified to include some of expected sodium parameters of ULOF transient described in chapter 1.3.4. The influence of these parameters on the outcome of the simulation gives a good indication over the suitability of water as a sodium simulant for the mock-up of boiling behaviour.

It is important to point out that the boundary conditions of the CHUG experimental conditions have been kept the same as the case involving water and steam. That is, the vapour, liquid and saturation temperatures are still the same employed in the previous section. Of course this does not correspond to a real situation, since sodium would still be solid at 20°C. However, in this analysis the interest is pointed towards the influence of properties such as surface tension and thermal conductivity. Thus, their influence can be better assessed by keeping the same boundary conditions of the previous presented simulation.

On the other hand, the sodium properties have to be extrapolated from the conditions of interest, namely from the conditions occurring during ULOF transient behaviour. Thus the liquid sodium properties are referred to a temperature of 570°C while the vapour sodium properties are referred to a temperature of 880°C, both at atmospheric pressure. The parameters are extrapolated from [53].

The results of two simulations are presented below. In the first one all the sodium properties are implemented but the thermal conductivity in order to study the influence of the surface tension. The second simulation is conducted after implementing also the thermal conductivity to evaluate the overall impact of sodium properties.

4.4.1 Surface tension

In this case all the sodium properties except from the thermal conductivity are implemented in order to study the influence of the surface tension on the bubble behaviour. The boundary conditions for sodium liquid and vapour are listed in Table 4.2. The grid configuration is the same as the water simulation and the injection of vapour is performed with a velocity equal to $1.0 \frac{m}{s}$.

The bubble behaviour is represented in Figure 4.16. Since the surface tension of sodium is significantly higher than the water one (almost one order of magnitude), it is visible how the volume of the bubble forming from the bottle-neck is bigger. The overall bubble behaviour before detachment is very

Table 4.2: Liquid and vapour sodium boundary conditions for the simulation of condensing bubble collapse performed by PSI-BOIL.

Property	Liquid	Vapour
Pressure	1 bar	1 bar
Temperature	20°C	151.8° C
Viscosity	2.146×10^{-4} Pa·s	2.488×10^{-5} Pa·s
Density	815 $\frac{kg}{m^3}$	0.281 $\frac{kg}{m^3}$
Specific Heat Capacity (C_p)	1256 $\frac{J}{kg \cdot K}$	2560 $\frac{J}{kg \cdot K}$
Thermal Conductivity	0.600 $\frac{W}{m \cdot K}$	0.03025 $\frac{W}{m \cdot K}$
Saturation Temperature		100°C
Surface Tension		0.15 $\frac{N}{m}$
Latent Heat		3.871×10^6 $\frac{J}{kg}$

similar to the one of water (Figure 4.11). A protuberance is generated at the top of the bubble surface due to the impulse given by the hydrostatic pressure gradient, triggering subsequent disturbances over the whole bubble. At the bubble root an enhanced necking effect is observable, as well as an inward recess due to the inclusion of the water jet.

However, it is fundamental to point out that the sodium bubble breaks up in very small parts right after detachment. This can be explained by looking at Figure 4.17, where the velocity and temperature fields are plotted. The higher value of the surface tension leads the bottle-neck connecting the vapour pocket and the vapour source to narrow even more than in case of water. This induces a huge upward current inside the bubble that, along with the development of a considerable liquid jet, causes the bubble to break up as soon as it detaches from the neck. This demonstrates that the necking phenomenon is responsible for the creation of the inner upward current inside the bubble. This, along with the lower value of viscosity owned by liquid sodium, leads the interface to be highly unstable at the moment of detachment and to the complete break-up of the bubble.

4.4.2 Thermal conductivity

In this case the thermal conductivities of sodium liquid ($\lambda_l = 60.62 \frac{W}{m \cdot K}$) and vapour ($\lambda_v = 0.0507 \frac{W}{m \cdot K}$) are implemented. Since the thermal conductivity is two order of magnitudes bigger than the water one, the injection velocity has been increased to $10 \frac{m}{s}$, otherwise the vapour would not have been even able to enter the system, due to the too strong condensation process.

As it is visible in Figure 4.18, even with an enhanced value of injection velocity the vapour column at the orifice is highly unstable and not able to produce bubbles. The condensation process is too strong and fast for bubbles to form and detach. Instead, the vapour column oscillates in the vertical direction and almost reaches the orifice. Thus, this explains the behaviour in ULOF transient, where an abrupt condensation occurs at the moment when the slug of sodium vapour reaches the colder liquid in the upper plenum.

The enhanced condensation can be viewed in Figure 4.19, where the heat transfer at the interface is highlighted along with the velocity field. It is visible how the strong condensation leads to a very unstable interface, which deforms considerably the velocity field. Due to abrupt condensation, the saturation temperature isoline at some instants falls inside the bubble, causing evaporation phenomena to occur at the interface.

The unstable behaviour of the bubble clearly shows how a high value of thermal conductivity leads to a great difference with the case of water. Even with enhanced injection velocity, the bubble is not able to detach from the vapour column. It is also important to keep in mind that the temperature difference between liquid and vapour is kept equal to the CHUG case. In the real situation the temperature difference, which drives the condensation process, is even higher ($\Delta T = 310K$). From this consideration, one can conclude that the formation of the slug of vapour inside the plenum during an ULOF transient is mainly due to the considerable drop in the hydrostatic pressure which leads to the abrupt expansion of the bubbles forming at the top of the active fuel part. Then, when the slug of vapour reaches the upper plenum, sudden and strong condensation occurs leading the vapour slug to abruptly collapse and cause the periodical behaviour identified as chugging.

Figure 4.16: Collapse of the condensing sodium bubble under CHUG experimental conditions simulated by PSI-BOIL (surface tension case).

Figure 4.17: Temperature and velocity fields during the collapse of the condensing sodium bubble under CHUG experimental conditions simulated by PSI-BOIL (surface tension case).

Figure 4.18: Collapse of the condensing sodium bubble under CHUG experimental conditons simulated by PSI-BOIL (thermal conductivity case).

Figure 4.19: Interface heat transfer and velocity fields during the collapse of the condensing sodium bubble under CHUG experimental conditions simulated by PSI-BOIL (thermal conductivity case). The saturation temperature iseline is highlighted in violet.

Chapter 5

Experimental Results

The experimental results included in this Thesis represent the first campaign of tests of the CHUG project. The aim of this first experimental campaign is to check the proper operation of every single component, including the data acquisition system, and to highlight the opportunities for improvement and development of the entire system.

Furthermore, it is important to verify if the chugging instability is actually reproduced by the CHUG facility and if the acquisition system is sufficient to capture all the phenomena envisaged by the objectives of the project. Even if the data from the first tests may not be used for a comprehensive analysis, it is useful to perform a preliminary assessment on the predictions made by pre-calculations, in particular the ones regarding the TRACE code. The assessment of the validity of PSI-BOIL calculations can be indeed performed only during the second phase of the CHUG project, when the acrylic glass section will make possible the visualization of the chugging instability by the use of a high speed camera.

This chapter is organized as follows. Firstly, an overview of the tests is given, where the parameters of the tests are presented. Several tests have been conducted by tuning the experimental parameters, in order to attempt to match the best conditions for the reproduction of the chugging phenomenon and to match TRACE pre-calculations. Secondly, the results from each test are presented highlighting the most important outcomes of the tests. Finally, an overall discussion of the experimental results is presented, where the data are compared with the analyses previously presented in this Thesis.

5.1 Tests overview

Recalling the experimental procedure already presented in Section 2.1, the aim of the experiment is the upward injection of steam produced by the steam generator into the test section, which is filled with water at ambient conditions, in order to reproduce the condensation regime of chugging. Thus, the main parameters that can be tuned in the experiment are the steam properties. In particular, the adjustment of the settings of the steam generator can regulate the initial steam pressure and the level of steam injection. Referring to the steam generator components in Figure 2.7 and Table 2.2, the pressure is regulated by the safety valve and the steam valve. The safety valve provides an upper pressure set-point, above which the steam present in the heater shell is no more heated in order to decrease steam pressure. The heater is then reactivated when the lower pressure set-point of the safety valve is reached, so that the pressure builds up again. This process tends to give an oscillating steam pressure parameter.

Meanwhile, when the steam flows out of the steam generator, the steam pressure inside the heater shell tends to decrease. The steam flow rate can be regulated by the steam valve, whose aperture is crucial for the stabilization of the steam mass flow. The steam valve can be adjusted so that an equilibrium between the build-up of pressure, due to the steam generation in the heater shell, and the decrease of pressure due to steam outflow is reached. This way the oscillations of the steam pressure and consequently of the steam injection rate can be minimized.

Since no flowmeter was available during the tests, the steam mass flow rate has been calculated by measuring the mass of water inside the test section at the beginning and at the end of the tests. The difference between these values, divided by the duration of the injection period, gives a good estimation of the mean mass flow rate injected during the test.

Another important parameter depending on the steam pressure and the injection rate is the steam temperature at the inlet of the test section. It is fundamental to consider the heat losses occurring along the steam line, from the steam generator to the test section. Since the steam line pipe is only 1 mm thick and is exposed to an environment with ambient temperature, the drop in temperature may be considerable depending on the steam flow rate. In order to minimize the heat losses and to deliver the steam into the test section with the highest possible temperature, a layer of insulating material has been applied to the external walls of the steam line.

Briefly, it can be said that the parameters of the experimental tests are tuned by the aperture of the steam valve, that is decisive, other than for the steam mass flow rate, both for the reaching of the pressure equilibrium inside the steam generator and for the steam temperature at the injection point. The parameters of the experimental tests performed during this Master's Thesis are summarized in Table 5.1.

Experimental tests		
Name	Parameter	Value
Test 1	Steam pressure	6.7 ± 0.3 bar
	Steam mass flow rate	0.70 ± 0.10 g/s
	Steam mass flux	25 ± 3 kg/(m ² ·s)
	Temperature at TS inlet	116 ± 2 °C
	Injection height	21 cm
	Pressure Sampling Frequency	51200 Samples/s
	Temperature Sampling Frequency	3 Samples/s
	Duration	185 s
Test 2	Steam pressure	$6.0 \text{ bar} \pm 0.3$ bar
	Steam mass flow rate	1.73 ± 0.10 g/s
	Steam mass flux	61 ± 3 kg/(m ² ·s)
	Temperature at TS inlet	121 ± 2 °C
	Injection height	21 cm
	Pressure Sampling Frequency	51200 Samples/s
	Temperature Sampling Frequency	3 Samples/s
	Duration	86 s
Test 3	Steam pressure	7.0 ± 0.3 bar
	Steam mass flow rate	1.20 ± 0.10 g/s
	Steam mass flux	42 ± 3 kg/(m ² ·s)
	Temperature at TS inlet	116 ± 2 °C
	Injection height	0 cm
	Pressure Sampling Frequency	51200 Samples/s
	Temperature Sampling Frequency	3 Samples/s
	Duration	80 s

Table 5.1: Parameters of the experimental tests performed in CHUG facility.

It must be pointed out that only two fixed thermocouples were available during these experimental tests, thus the temperature measurements covered only the first two thermocouple axial positions ($h = 25\text{cm}, 70\text{cm}$). The thermocouple at 25 cm from the bottom is crucial since it is placed close to the injection point and monitors the heat-up of water in the lower part of the test section. It is fundamental not to prolong the test when the water temperature exceeds 100°C, since high temperatures can endanger the integrated electronic circuit inside the piezoelectric pressure sensor. The thermocouple at the second axial position is useful to give an idea of the level of thermal stratification occurring during the test for a first comparison with the pre-calculations performed by TRACE code.

Finally, it is important to mention that during the performance of the experimental tests presented in this Thesis the position of the injection point has been varied. In the first two tests the steam flowed through the inner bent steam pipe and was injected in the center at a height equal to 21 cm. In order to investigate the influence of the injection point on the results, Test 3 has been performed while removing the inner pipe and by injecting steam directly at the bottom of the test section, through the dedicated hole for the steam line, which is 17 mm distant from the center of the test section.

5.1.1 Test 1: Low steam mass flux

Test 1 has been performed with low injection rate, corresponding to a steam mass flux of $25 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s})$. In Figures 5.1 and 5.2 the dynamic pressure measurement of the piezoelectric pressure sensor and the temperature measurement of the thermocouples are depicted.

Figure 5.1: Test 1 - Dynamic pressure measurement acquired by the piezoelectric pressure sensor at the bottom of the test section. The average centerline is highlighted in orange.

It is important to point out again that only dynamic pressure is detected, so no information on the static pressure can be inferred. Continuous positive and negative pressure peaks develop throughout the whole test, meaning that the oscillating chugging behaviour is reproduced and detected. However, it is possible to notice in Figure 5.1 that during the first 50 seconds the average centerline (highlighted in orange) assumes negative values. This is unexpected since, due to the nature of the pressure sensor that does not measure changes in static pressure, the average centerline should remain as close as possible to zero, not showing drifts from the horizontal zero line.

This anomaly is related to a temperature-induced drift affecting the pressure sensor. When a piezoelectric pressure sensor is heated up two disturbing effects may occur:

- The expansion of the piezoelectric crystal produces a stretch in the sensing elements that then tend to measure a negative pressure;

Figure 5.2: Test 1 - Temperature measurements acquired by the thermocouples at two different axial positions (TC1: $z = 25\text{cm}$; TC2: $z = 70\text{cm}$).

- The increase of temperature of the pressure sensor leads the integrated electronic circuit to heat up causing anomalous measurements to occur.

The expansion of the piezoelectric crystal is already assessed through a value of temperature sensitivity present in the specifications provided by the manufacturer. In the CHUG project the piezoelectric crystal has a temperature sensitivity change of 0.05% per Degree Celsius. This does not justify the presence of a temperature drift leading to an average negative pressure down to -0.2 bar. Thus the principal cause of this temperature drift is attributed to the heat-up of the integrated electronic circuit. In any case, the anomaly causes a significant temperature drift that must be corrected before analysing the results.

It must be mentioned that both effects occur only during continuous variation of the temperature, whereas when the temperature is stabilised the temperature-induced drift does not occur. Examining the temperature plot of Figure 5.2 it is noticeable that, while the first thermocouple near the injection point undergoes a continuous increase of temperature, the second thermocouple placed 50 cm above the injection point maintains roughly a stable temperature for the first 50 seconds and then starts increasing slowly. This can lead to the conclusion that the heat-up of water occurs in the first place at the bottom of the test section due to the heat exchange with the hot steam flowing through the inner injection pipe. Therefore, the pressure sensor, placed at the bottom of the test section, experiences an increase of temperature for approximately 50 seconds, after which also the temperature in the upper part of the test section starts increasing. This also justifies why the temperature-induced drift on the pressure sensor is significantly present for 50 seconds, after which the average centerline of the pressure measurement starts stabilizing around the horizontal zero line and only undergoes minor oscillations.

On the other hand, it can be visible that at the end of the test, when the injection of steam ceases after the closure of the injection valve, the decrease of temperature at the pressure sensor due to inner recirculation and mixing produces a positive temperature drift. As expected, the value of the drift due to the temperature decrease is opposite to the one at the beginning, when the temperature increases. This is an additional proof of the presence of the temperature-induced drift on the pressure sensor.

In order to solve the problem of the temperature drift, it is fundamental to track the water temperature at the pressure sensor position. Future steps of the project envisage a new thermocouple measurement at the bottom of the test section in order to detect the variations of temperature causing the drift. By transmitting the data to the sensor provider it will be possible to quantify the influence of temperature on the pressure measurement and to correct accurately the future measurements performed by the piezoelectric crystal by removing the temperature-induced drift. Another approach would be to substitute the currently utilised IEPE sensor with a new one without built-in electronics, to eliminate the problem of electronic parts being heated up.

For the present study, in order to use the data for the analysis, the pressure measurements have been corrected in a rough but astute way. By the use of the moving average algorithm (with a selection of $N = 51200$ points) it was possible to reconstruct the trend of the average centerline (shown in orange in Figure 5.1) and to subtract it from the actual pressure measurement. This way the temperature drift has been eliminated. It must be pointed out that this "brutal" approach has been undertaken with the purpose of studying only the trend of the pressure oscillations. Since this is a preliminary experimental study, it has been fundamental to investigate which phenomena take place in the facility in order to verify if the chugging phenomenon is reproduced. For a more precise quantitative assessment, a proper and thorough approach has to be developed for the correction of the data collected by the pressure sensor.

Figure 5.3: Test 1 - Corrected dynamic pressure measurement acquired by the piezoelectric pressure sensor at the bottom of the test section: the temperature drift has been removed.

The corrected pressure measurement, where the temperature drift has been removed, is presented in Figure 5.3. It is apparent that a strong oscillatory behaviour is reproduced, with peaks of pressure up to 3.25 bar. In Figure 5.4 the pressure signal is analysed at four different instants of the test during an interval of 3 seconds each.

At the beginning of the test, when the temperature at the injection point is around 25°C (TC1 measurement in Figure 5.2), weak pressure spikes with a maximum of around 0.5 bar develop. However, it must be noticed that the negative dynamic pressure dips are stronger than the positive peaks. This effect

Figure 5.4: Test 1 - Details of the dynamic pressure measurement obtained by zooming at 4 different 3-second periods during the test.

can be explained as follows. When the bubble formed at the injection point starts condensing, a pressure drop is felt from the sensor since water from the bottom of the test section is sucked upwards towards the injection point. On the other hand, due to the low steam mass flux, an internal chugging regime as described in Section 1.5 is likely to occur at the first instants of the test. Thus, the oscillations of the vapour-liquid interface may occur within the steam injection pipe and the pressure waves may propagate mainly along the steam line, showing only peaks of lower magnitude at the piezoelectric pressure sensor. In order to verify this, an additional pressure sensor should be installed in the steam line, in a similar way as most of the experimental apparatus for the detection of direct contact condensation highlighted in Section 1.5.

Another effect that cannot be neglected is the heat exchange between the steam flowing through the inner injection pipe and the cold water at the bottom of the test section at the first instants of the test. Steam superheat is thus reduced before the vapour comes in contact with the water pool and consequently the oscillations of the interface may occur only inside the steam line.

After the bottom of the test section has been heated up, around 60 seconds after the beginning of the test, occasional stronger pressure spikes develop reaching up to 2 bar. The behaviour of the pressure oscillations resembles the one highlighted for internal chugging in Figure 1.12 and taken from [21]: after a negative dip in the dynamic pressure due to the condensation of the steam that draws water from the surroundings, a strong pressure peak is detected followed by the so-called "ring-out" pressure oscillations at high frequency. The ring-out interval may generally contain frequency components resulting from acoustic effects in the pool water column. Moreover, the influence of the test section structure on the pressure sensor must be taken into account. Every time a chug occurs, the pressure spike developed leads to the vibration of the whole test section. Since the piezoelectric pressure sensor is highly sensitive, the high-frequency vibrations are detected and may constitute part of the ring-out following the strong peak.

After approximately 60 seconds of test, the temperature at the injection point has reached almost 50°C. It can be then supposed that the change of pressure behaviour at that point may occur due to the replacement of internal chugging with external chugs following the detachment of the bubble, as highlighted from the regime map of Figure 1.11 [20]. However, the analysis cannot be fully based on this regime map since it was obtained by a downward injection case.

Stronger and more frequent pressure spikes develop after 111 seconds from the beginning of the test, when the temperature at the injection point exceeds 60°C. Above this temperature the internal chugging regime is unlikely to occur. However, the behaviour of the pressure spikes still closely resembles the one highlighted for this case in Figure 1.12, obtained during downward injection conditions. This leads to the conclusion that in case of upward injection the conditions for chugging are extended and the pressure spikes are even more violent, as already pointed out in [23].

The most unexpected and interesting outcome of this test concerns the pressure behaviour after around three minutes of test, when the temperature at the injection point reaches approximately 75°C. The water subcooling is so restricted that a bubbling regime is expected according to the regime maps presented in Section 1.5. However, strong pressure peaks keep on occurring with higher frequency than before. This highlights a very interesting behaviour that can be explained by investigating the temperature measurements in Figure 5.2. During the test, a strong thermal stratification occurs. As already mentioned, temperature at the second thermocouple position ($z = 70\text{cm}$) starts increasing constantly only after 50 seconds, when the bottom of the test section is already heated up. Moreover, the temperature difference between the two thermocouple positions appears to be constant afterwards and equal to 35°C.

Thermal stratification may be decisive for the development of strong chugs even when the subcooling at the injection point has been considerably reduced. It can be assumed that a steam pocket develops inside the test section detaching from the injection pipe and rising up due to buoyancy forces. When the steam pocket reaches the cold water in the upper part of the test section it gets condensed very quickly, causing the upper and lower liquid fronts to accelerate and collapse into each other, producing a strong pressure wave detected by the piezoelectric pressure sensor.

Figure 5.5: Test 1 - Single-sided amplitude spectrum obtained from the FFT corrected dynamic pressure signal acquired by the piezoelectric pressure sensor at the bottom of the test section.

The single-sided amplitude spectrum obtained by the application of the Fast Fourier Transform to the dynamic pressure signal is depicted in logarithmic scale in Figure 5.5. The dominant frequency of the pressure signal is around 1 Hz. This is in contrast with the findings from TRACE pre-calculations, where no low frequency component appears to be excited. On the other hand, the pressure signal locks down into a low frequency range close to the manometer mode, as predicted by the linear stability analysis from [27], which indicates a chugging frequency around 1 Hz. In the amplitude spectrum of Figure 5.5 it is noticeable how the range of frequencies from 1 to 20 Hz are excited, with a visible peak at 6 Hz in line with the predictions from TRACE.

It is possible to explain the lack of low frequency excitation in TRACE if the strong oscillating behaviour occurring at the end of the test due to thermal stratification is considered. Since TRACE is not able to reproduce the thermal stratification in the test section, the strong repetitive pressure peaks at the end of the calculation are not included in the amplitude spectrum and consequently the very-low-frequency range is not excited.

Finally, it is visible that a wide range of frequencies from 20 Hz to 100 Hz appear to be weakly excited in the test. This range corresponds to the high-frequency components, characteristic of the acoustic effects of the ring-out oscillations. Furthermore, the high-frequency range may be excited by vibrations of the structure and the noise of the pressure sensor, which are not of particular interest in this analysis.

5.1.2 Test 2: High steam mass flux

Test 2 has been performed with high injection rate, corresponding to a steam mass flux of $61 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s})$. In Figures 5.6 and 5.7 the dynamic pressure measurement of the piezoelectric pressure sensor and the temperature measurement of the thermocouples are depicted, respectively.

In Figure 5.8 the temperature-induced drift affecting the pressure sensor has been removed by the method explained in the previous section.

The test ran for a shorter time (86 seconds of injection) with respect to Test 1, since the higher steam mass flux lead to a fast temperature increase at the injection point, causing the saturation temperature

Figure 5.6: Test 2 - Dynamic pressure measurement acquired by the piezoelectric pressure sensor at the bottom of the test section. The average centerline is highlighted in orange.

Figure 5.7: Test 2 - Temperature measurement acquired by the thermocouples at two different axial positions (TC1: $z = 25cm$; TC2: $z = 70cm$).

to be reached. The test has been then stopped to preserve the integrity and safety of the piezoelectric pressure, which can work only in a restricted range of temperature.

Figure 5.8: Test 2 - Corrected dynamic pressure measurement acquired by the piezoelectric pressure sensor at the bottom of the test section: the temperature drift has been removed.

The pressure signal shows high frequency oscillations with a maximum peak of pressure higher than 2.5 bar towards the end of the test. In order to investigate the detailed behaviour of the pressure oscillations, a zoom into intervals of 3 seconds at four different instants of the test is displayed in Figure 5.9.

At the beginning of the test ($t = 5s$), when the temperature at the injection point is around 25°C (TC1 measurement in Figure 5.7), high-frequency pressure spikes with a maximum of around 0.5 bar develop. The frequency of the pressure oscillations is sensibly higher than in Test 1. This proves the presence of the so-called condensation oscillations, described in Section 1.5 and displayed in Figure 1.12. The high steam injection rate causes the steam bubble, attached to the injection tube exit, not to collapse completely, but to grow and shrink alternately. The movement of the interface governs the pressure oscillations that are characterised by a high-frequency component. As the temperature quickly increases, the oscillation frequency becomes smaller due to the decrease of subcooling at the injection point. This leads to a delay in the succession between growth and shrinking of the bubble, since the condensation effects are weakened.

At $t = 35s$, when the temperature of water at the injection point has reached already 65°C , the pressure oscillations keep the configuration of condensation oscillations, but occur with lower frequency. Due to the lower subcooling at the injection point, bubbles detach from the injection pipe and a high frequency bubbling regime takes place. When the bubbles get condensed in the colder upper region of the test section, pressure waves propagate towards the bottom of the test section and are detected by the pressure sensor.

At $t = 57s$ the reduction of the oscillation frequency is stronger and it is accompanied by an increase in magnitude of the pressure spikes. At this moment, the temperature at the injection point is around 80°C . The temperature difference with respect to the second thermocouple is very large, up to 50°C , highlighting more pronounced thermal stratification, if compared to the results from Test 1. Bubbles detaching from the injection point rise through the high-temperature zone and collapse when they

Figure 5.9: Test 2 - Details of the dynamic pressure measurement obtained by zooming at 4 different 3-second periods during the test.

reach the low-temperature area. The collapse of the bubbles cause the upper and lower liquid fronts to bump into each other and pressure spikes with higher magnitude develop. This behaviour is similar to the one detected in Test 1, but occurs with higher frequency due to the higher steam injection mass flow rate.

During the last instants of Test 2 ($t = 76s$), the regime changes again. Low frequency bubbling takes place due to the considerably small subcooling. Bubbles, generated with lower frequency, may coalesce forming a steam pocket rising through the test section. The collapse of the steam pocket occurs with lower frequency than during the previous interval, but generates very strong spikes. The maximum pressure peak is indeed detected at $t = 82s$, few seconds before the injection of steam is stopped.

Figure 5.10: Test 2 - Single-sided amplitude spectrum obtained from the FFT corrected dynamic pressure signal acquired by the piezoelectric pressure sensor at the bottom of the test section.

The single-sided amplitude spectrum obtained by the application of the Fast Fourier Transform to the dynamic pressure signal is depicted in logarithmic scale in Figure 5.10. A profound difference can be noticed if this amplitude spectrum is compared to the one of Test 1. The low-frequency range between 0.1 Hz and 1 Hz is still excited, but the high steam mass flux and the presence of condensation oscillations causes the high frequency range (between 10 Hz and 100 Hz) to be dominant. In particular, the most dominant frequencies appear to be around 15 Hz and 30 Hz. Thus, as predicted by [26, 27], the pressure oscillations tend to lock into the first acoustic mode.

The excitation of frequencies higher than 100 Hz are due to the vibrations of the structure and the noise of the pressure sensor, which are not of particular interest in this analysis.

5.1.3 Test 3: Injection from the bottom

In Test 3 the injection tube inside the test section has been removed. This allows the influence of the position of the injection point on the experimental results to be investigated. An intermediate injection rate, if compared to the previous tests, has been chosen and corresponds to a steam mass flux of $42 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s})$

Steam was injected only for 80 seconds in order not to exceed the maximum working temperature of the piezoelectric pressure sensor. Since steam is injected close to the pressure sensor, the heat-up of the

bottom of the test section is more rapid than in the previous cases and the test length results to be the shortest.

In Figures 5.11 and 5.12 the dynamic pressure measurement of the piezoelectric pressure sensor and the temperature measurement of the thermocouples are depicted, respectively.

Figure 5.11: Test 3 - Dynamic pressure measurement acquired by the piezoelectric pressure sensor at the bottom of the test section. The average centerline is highlighted in orange.

As it may be noticed in Figure 5.11, the temperature-induced drift is more pronounced than in the previous cases. Since the injection point is placed right next to the pressure sensor, a faster and more enhanced heat-up takes place and has a stronger effect on the pressure sensor. Moreover, towards the end of the test, when the subcooling at the bottom of the test section is considerably low, bigger steam pockets may form due to coalescence of bubbles and reach the pressure sensor, producing a very unstable behaviour in the pressure signal. Thus, the readings from the pressure sensor are complex to analyse, since it is not clear in what extent the temperature drift affects the detection of the pressure oscillation. An attempt to correct the drift has been made by decreasing the number of samples ($N = 12800$) in the moving average algorithm explained above, resulting in the average centerline of Figure 5.11. The corrected pressure measurement, where the temperature drift has been removed, is presented in Figure 5.3.

Figure 5.11 shows how in this case, significantly stronger pressure spikes develop throughout the whole test, with a maximum of 5 bar. Even during the first instants of injection the average magnitude of the pressure oscillations is higher, highlighting a strong influence of the injection point on the pressure signal detected by the piezoelectric pressure sensor. This may be due to the fact that the pressure sensor is significantly closer to the injection point and it can be thus able to detect all the pressure waves generating from the interface movement of the steam bubbles, without damping of the water column standing above it as in the previous cases. In Figure 5.14, a zoom into an interval of 5 seconds at the beginning of the test is depicted.

The graph of pressure oscillations presents an intermediate behaviour with respect to those of Tests

Figure 5.12: Test 3 - Temperature measurement acquired by the thermocouples at two different axial positions (TC1: $z = 25\text{cm}$; TC2: $z = 70\text{cm}$).

Figure 5.13: Test 3 - Corrected dynamic pressure measurement acquired by the piezoelectric pressure sensor at the bottom of the test section: the temperature drift has been removed.

Figure 5.14: Test 3 - Detail of the dynamic pressure measurement obtained by zooming at the 5-second period right after the start of the injection.

1 and 2. At the beginning of the test ($t = 7s$) the shape of the oscillations recalls the small chugging pressure oscillations represented in Figure 1.12. Strong chugs develop with low frequency as in the case of internal chugging, but the high-frequency component characteristic of condensation oscillations is dominant. It must be noticed that the magnitude of the pressure peaks reaches up to 2 bar, significantly higher than in the previous investigated cases. This may be explained by the closer exposure of the pressure sensor to the injection point, which leads to the detection of all the pressure waves released by the interface movement.

Towards the end of the test the dominant frequency is reduced, since the bubbles formed at the injection point tend to rise along an elongating path through the test section before collapsing. Very high pressure peaks are detected, suggesting that large steam slugs may form in the test section. The collapse of these slugs causes a strong acceleration of the liquid fronts which bump into each other at high velocity and generate a very strong pressure wave. However, the pressure signal at the end of the test may be seriously affected by the temperature drift, so these hypotheses have to be carefully evaluated.

Thermal stratification is significantly pronounced even in this case. It must be recalled that the reading from the first thermocouple does not represent the temperature close to the injection point. That is why a latency in its heat-up is observed. However, the water column gets heated up quickly and at the end of the test a temperature of 80°C is detected at $z = 25\text{cm}$.

The single-sided amplitude spectrum obtained by the application of the Fast Fourier Transform to the dynamic pressure signal is depicted in logarithmic scale in Figure 5.15. The proof that an intermediate situation between internal chugging and condensation oscillations is reached is the fact that the low- and high-frequency ranges are comparably excited. The dominant frequency is between 6 and 7 Hz, but peaks are observable both at 1 Hz and 20 Hz. Thus, both chugging and condensation oscillation frequency components are present in this case.

The excitation of frequencies higher than 100 Hz occurs due to the vibrations of the structure and the noise of the pressure sensor, which are not of particular interest in this analysis.

5.1.4 Discussion

The results from the three tests presented above highlight that the chugging phenomenon is well reproduced by CHUG experimental facility. In particular, by varying the level of injection, several patterns of pressure oscillations have been reproduced. The detected regimes are in accordance with previous studies on Direct Contact Condensation presented in Section 1.5.

The most important outcome of the experimental results is the possibility to reproduce different pat-

Figure 5.15: Test 3 - Single-sided amplitude spectrum obtained from the FFT corrected dynamic pressure signal acquired by the piezoelectric pressure sensor at the bottom of the test section.

terns of oscillations along the same test. This is possible thanks to the configuration of CHUG facility. Unlike experimental campaigns presented in the past, an upward steam injection is realized into a test section containing a small volume of water, contrarily to large water pools employed for the study of BWR pressure suppression pools. This leads to an enhanced thermal stratification that leads to capture later bubbling regimes of profound interest in the frame of the ESFR-SMART project.

The possible formation of vapour slugs rising through the test section and collapsing in an upper low-temperature area, accelerating the upper and lower liquid fronts towards each other and leading to the generation of strong chugs, recalls indeed what has been simulated during ULOF scenarios in SFRs, as described in Section 1.3.4. This may represent a way to mock up the oscillating behaviour of sodium boiling in low-void core concepts, where the sodium vapour slug forming at the top of the active fuel zone expands until it gets abruptly condensed by the colder liquid sodium present in the upper plenum. Naturally, the limited experimental data used during this analysis (only one pressure and two temperature measurements) do not give a clear confirmation of the hypotheses developed in this Chapter. The acrylic glass test section to be implemented in phase two of the CHUG project will allow the visualization of the steam behaviour inside the facility and the verification of all the hypotheses. If the latter will be confirmed, the principal objective of CHUG project, namely the mock-up of sodium boiling in low-void SFR core concepts by the use of water as a simulant, can be considered as accomplished.

An important objective of the CHUG project is the assessment of the validity of the thermal-hydraulics code TRACE in the reproduction of the chugging boiling regime. From the experimental results obtained several considerations can be made.

TRACE is able to reproduce the pressure oscillations due to the chugging phenomenon. The magnitude of the pressure spikes predicted by the 2D model of TRACE is consistent with the pressure measured at the bottom of the test section during the first instants of the test. On the other hand, the 1D model tends to exaggerate the magnitude of the pressure spikes: peaks up to 40 bar are probably simulated due to the water packing effect and do not have consistency with the maximum magnitude detected during the experimental tests (the maximum peak is around 5 bar).

However, the difference between chugging and the high-frequency condensation oscillations is not captured by TRACE, which always reproduces oscillations with a dominant frequency around 5 Hz. The reason for this restricted capability of TRACE can be explained by the fact that very small time steps have to be necessarily employed in order to resolve contact condensation. Moreover, the phenomena occurring at the interface cannot be captured due to the intrinsic properties of thermal hydraulics codes, which are not able to resolve the steam-water interface. That is why new approaches and models have been recently developed for the simulation of direct contact condensation in pressure suppression pool, as in [31].

An important consequence of the missing capture of the direct contact condensation phenomenon is the complete lack of thermal stratification predicted by TRACE. The temperature experimental data are totally inconsistent with the findings from the TRACE pre-calculations. In TRACE there tends to be a complete mixing of the water pool that leads a very restricted temperature difference between the axial layers of the test section. Consequently, TRACE pre-calculations tend to underestimate the heat-up of the water pool: the whole volume of water inside the test section tends to heat up simultaneously resulting in a higher thermal inertia and in a limited increase of pool temperature. The strong boundary condition applied to the TRACE model, where the external surface temperature was fixed to 20°C, may reinforce this effect. However, even the sensitivity case without heat structure of Section 3.4.4 is not able to represent such a heat-up of the bottom of the water pool and neither the thermal stratification.

Since thermal stratification is not reproduced by TRACE, the results from the pre-calculations can be compared only with the first instants of the tests, where the conditions are comparable to the boundary condition given to TRACE. The strong pressure spikes detected at the end of the test and due to the rise of steam pockets through the thermally-stratified test section cannot be compared, since the water pool conditions do not match. However, since direct contact condensation is not simulated by TRACE, vapour slugs tend to develop during TRACE simulations, as it is visible by the 1D case void map of Figure 3.8. In the 1D TRACE pre-calculation the behaviour detected during the last instants of the experimental tests may be reproduced, even if at different boundary conditions. The strong spikes developing in the 1D case simulation can then be related to this behaviour but are anyway exaggerated by the water packing effect. It must be recalled that only the 1D case outlined a very weak thermal stratification of the pool.

In order to be able to reproduce the thermal stratification in TRACE calculations, future works envisage the implementation of targeted boundary conditions at the heat structure that could promote the presence of layers of water at different temperature. For instance, the constant outer surface temperature condition can be replaced by specifying a heat transfer coefficient varying along the height of the heat structure. This way the heat losses through the wall can be differentiated axially and different temperature may appear axially in the water pool.

In synthesis, TRACE 2D model is able to reproduce the magnitude of the pressure peaks due to the chugging behaviour but it is not able to capture the direct contact condensation phenomena occurring in the test section. In particular, TRACE tends to predict a complete mixing of the water pool while enhanced thermal stratification is detected in the experimental tests. Moreover, TRACE predicts the formation and collapse of slugs of vapour rising through the test section similarly to what observed during the final instants of the experimental tests, even if at different water pool conditions. This sets a difficult challenge for the reproduction of thermally-stratified pools of TRACE and for the mock-up of real experimental conditions, but it can be seen as a positive aspect for the simulation of ULOF transient in SFRs, where this behaviour is well represented along with a sensible temperature difference between the fuel sub-assembly and the upper plenum.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

The main objective of this Master's Thesis has been the design and realisation of the experimental water rig facility "CHUG" in the frame of the ESRF-SMART European project. Previous analyses of ULOF accidents in low-void SFR core design highlighted the possible occurrence of a stabilised chugging boiling regime, that can have dramatic impact on the intrinsic safety of Sodium-cooled Fast Reactors. The aim of the CHUG facility is to mock up the sodium boiling regime in order to analyse the conditions for the occurrence of the chugging thermal-hydraulic instability and to assess the capability of thermal hydraulics codes like TRACE to simulate this type of oscillating behaviour.

In the frame of this Master's Thesis the CHUG facility has been designed and built in the Laboratory of Reactor Physics and Systems Behaviour at EPFL. The design phase has been supported by pre-calculations realized with TRACE. Furthermore, simulations of bubble condensation in subcooled liquid were performed with PSI's in-house CFD code PSI-BOIL in order to study the bubble collapse under the conditions of the CHUG experiment. Finally, the first experimental tests have been performed and compared to TRACE pre-calculations.

The results out of the TRACE 2D model show that pressure oscillations typical of chugging behaviour are reproduced. The oscillating behaviour of the interface at the injection point is roughly simulated. Steam-water mixing at the injection leads to the collapse of vapour slugs inside the test section and to pressure peaks up to 8 bar at the bottom of the test section. The dominant frequency of the pressure oscillations is around 5 Hz. However, no thermal stratification is reproduced by TRACE, but a complete steam-water mixing occurs. This may be attributed to the incomplete condensation of a part of the bubbles that rise until the free level of the test section causing an uniform heat-up.

A sensitivity study on several parameters of the TRACE model has been performed. Firstly, the influence of the modelling properties was assessed. A 1D model of the CHUG facility has been built for the comparison with the multi-1D channel representation usually performed during SFR safety analyses. The results obtained by employing the 1D model highlight the simulation of pressure peaks up to 40 bar at the bottom of the test section. The presence of such considerable peaks is due to the water packing effect. The void fraction axial profile over time is comparable to the one obtained by the simulation of ULOF transient in low-void SFR core concept, highlighting the possibility of sodium boiling mock-up. Both axial and radial refinement of CHUG 2D model causes the damping of the pressure oscillations at the bottom of the cross section with no substantial improvement on the prediction of thermal stratification. The removal of the heat structure leads to the disappearance of the chugging phenomenon when the water subcooling becomes too low, as expected from the condensation regime maps developed in previous study, but does not solve the problem of the lack of thermal stratification.

The second part of the sensitivity study focused on the influence of the initial conditions. The increase of the steam injection mass flow rate shows pressure oscillations with lower magnitude. This may highlight the possible simulation of condensation oscillations, even if their typical high-frequency components are not excited the frequency amplitude spectrum. A sinusoidal injection case similar to what presented in the previous study from the author has been

conducted: the frequency spectrum does not undergo significant changes with respect to previous cases, highlighting the independence of the chugging boiling regime from the neutronic feedback effects.

PSI-BOIL pre-calculations have been realised by employing a coarse grid and boundary conditions representative of CHUG experimental tests. The results show that the behaviour of a bubble collapsing in a subcooled water pool is reproduced by PSI-BOIL consistently with the findings from previous studies. The formation of an upward liquid jet is well highlighted in the results as well as the disturbances generated due to the enhanced condensation process and gravity effects. However, the coarseness of the grid does not allow a deep investigation on the thermal boundary layer at the bubble surface, which anyway does not have a stable behaviour due to numerical instabilities caused by the fast condensation process. The liquid inertia driven collapse is only partly reproduced and the influence of heat transfer effects is not negligible. The lack of the compressibility properties of water does not allow capturing all the phenomena related to the collapse of bubbles at high Ja values.

The boundary conditions of PSI-BOIL simulation of CHUG experiment have been modified to include some of expected sodium parameters occurring during ULOF transient. In the first case, all the sodium properties except from the thermal conductivity are implemented in order to study the influence of surface tension on the bubble behaviour. Since the surface tension of sodium is significantly higher than the water one, the volume of the bubbles forming during the simulation is bigger. The overall bubble behaviour before detachment is very similar to the one of water. However, the sodium bubble breaks up in very small parts right after detachment due to an enhanced necking phenomenon that accelerates the injected vapour through the vapour pocket, rendering the interface highly unstable. In the second case, also the thermal conductivity of sodium is implemented. The results highlight the high instability of the vapour column at the interface that hinders bubble formation. This is caused by the too strong and fast condensation processes, highlighting a profound difference with water.

The experimental results highlight that the chugging phenomenon is well reproduced by CHUG experimental facility. The variation of the level of injection allows the reproduction of several patterns of pressure oscillations. The detected regimes are in accordance with previous studies on Direct Contact Condensation presented in Section 1.5. A very important outcome of the experimental results is the opportunity to reproduce different patterns of oscillations along the same test. This is possible thanks to the configuration of CHUG facility, where an upward steam injection is realized into a test section containing a small volume of water. Unlike experimental studies presented in the past, where downward steam injection into large water pools was employed for the study of BWR pressure suppression pools, the CHUG experimental configuration enhances the axial thermal stratification, which is fundamental for the reproduction of collapse of vapour slugs during the bubbling regime, of profound interest in the frame of the ESRF-SMART project.

Test 1, performed with low injection rate, highlights the presence of pressure oscillations resembling the ones typical of the internal chugging regime, with dominant frequency of approximately 1 Hz occurs. On the other hand, Test 2 was conducted with high injection rate, showing high-frequency condensation oscillations weaker than in the case of low injection rate.

Test 3 was carried out with an intermediate injection rate and the relocation of the injection point at the bottom of the test section. A transitional regime between internal chugging and condensation oscillation occurs, while strong chugs arises repeatedly. Pressure oscillations have higher magnitude due to the closer exposure of the pressure sensor to the relocated injection point.

In all three experimental tests the strongest pressure spikes (up to 5 bar) occur towards the end of the injection interval, when a bubbling regime is expected due to the low subcooling around the injection point. The enhanced axial thermal stratification induces the formation of vapour slugs rising through the test section and collapsing in the upper low-temperature area. The upper and lower liquid fronts are thus accelerated towards each other and major pressure waves are generated. This recalls the oscillatory scenario known as stabilised boiling which has been simulated during ULOF scenarios in SFRs. Thus, this may represent a way to mock up the oscillating behaviour of sodium boiling in low-void core concepts, where the sodium vapour slug forming at the top of the active fuel zone expands until it gets abruptly condensed by the colder liquid sodium present in the upper plenum.

The experimental results were compared to the analytical results pre-calculated by the thermal hydraulics code TRACE. The 2D model is able to reproduce the magnitude of the pressure peaks characteristic of chugging behaviour, but it is not capable to simulate the direct contact condensation phenomena occurring in the test section. In particular, TRACE tends to predict a complete mixing of the water pool while enhanced thermal stratification is detected in the experimental tests. Moreover, TRACE 1D model predicts the formation and collapse of slugs of vapour rising through the test section similarly to what observed during the final instants of the experimental tests, even if at different water pool conditions. The peaks of pressure are nevertheless overestimated by TRACE, due the strong water packing effect. This sets a difficult challenge for the reproduction of thermally-stratified pools of TRACE and for the mock-up of real experimental conditions.

6.1 Future prospects

The limited experimental data used during this analysis (only one pressure signal and two thermocouple measurements) do not clearly confirm the hypotheses developed in this Thesis. The acrylic glass test section along with the high speed camera that is to be implemented in phase two of the CHUG project will allow the visualization of the steam behaviour inside the facility and the verification of all the hypotheses. Another option under consideration is the installation of a wire-mesh sensor, a flow imaging technique allowing the investigation of the void fraction distribution over the tube cross section with high spatial and temporal resolution, for the recording of the bubbling regime developing at the late instants of the test.

In any case, if the hypotheses presented in this Thesis will be confirmed, the principal objective of CHUG project, namely the mock-up of sodium boiling in low-void SFR core concepts by the use of water as a simulant, can be considered as accomplished.

Phase two of the CHUG project will be also fundamental for the validation of PSI-BOIL pre-calculations performed in Chapter 4, where the CHUG steam and water conditions have been matched to investigate the behaviour of bubble collapse in subcooled water. Unfortunately, the experimental data obtained in this Master's Thesis do not allow a first assessment of the validity of PSI-BOIL simulations. This remains an objective of CHUG project to be reached. In any case, future studies are planned for the implementation of sodium properties into PSI-BOIL in order to simulate sodium boiling occurring at the upper region of low-void SFR core sub-assemblies during ULOF transients.

CHUG facility has several margins for the improvement of the experimental data quality. The most important problem concerns the temperature-induced drift affecting the pressure signal and occurring due to the exposition of the pressure sensor to strong gradients of temperature. As already mentioned, it is fundamental to add a thermocouple measurement at the bottom of the test section to track the variation of temperature felt by the pressure sensor. These data will then be sent to the pressure sensor manufacturer, who will be able to disclose more information regarding this effect and hopefully provide a thorough correction curve that will enable to improve the quality of the pressure measurement. An alternative option would be the acquisition of a pressure sensor without an integrated electronic circuit, that would cancel the issues of the temperature drift.

The next experimental tests envisage also the placement of the thermocouple at the highest axial position, already envisaged in the experiment design but not available during this Master's Thesis project. The use of a higher number of thermocouples is also envisaged for future steps, in order to track more accurately the thermal stratification occurring inside the test section.

Another margin for improvement is the use of a flowmeter installed in the steam line in order to track a more accurate value of the injection steam mass flow rate along with potential time variations. This will give the possibility to target and tune exactly the level of injection at any time during the tests. Furthermore, it will give more indications about the interface behaviour during the chugging phenomenon. A further improvement for the experimental analysis would be the placement of an additional pressure sensor in the steam line. The related pressure signal would be a good indicator for the pressure waves

propagating along the injection tube during internal chugging and a good term of comparison for the pressure sensor at the bottom of the test section.

Finally, new TRACE calculations are envisaged in future with the attempt to match the experimental conditions. TRACE pre-calculations highlighted the lack of capability of TRACE to reproduce the axial thermal stratification occurring as steam is injected into the test section. The formation of slugs of vapour rising through the test section and abruptly collapsing is simulated by the 1D model, but the fluid conditions are significantly different from the experimental ones. Thus, the comparison between the analytical and experimental results is not exhaustive.

Future works envisage the implementation of targeted boundary conditions. For instance, the constant outer surface temperature condition can be replaced by specifying a heat transfer coefficient varying along the height of the heat structure. This way the heat losses through the wall can be differentiated axially and that could promote the presence of layers of water at different temperature

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